

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 3.4
Elaborati di progetto
esecutivo riguardanti gli
interventi sugli edifici pilota

Poročilo 3.4
Celoten projekt za izvedbo
potresne utrditve pilotnih
stavb

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 3.4

Executive design documents concerning the interventions on the pilot buildings

NOVEMBER 2025

Authors: Gattesco N.⁽¹⁾, Boem I.⁽¹⁾, Rizzi E.⁽¹⁾, Saveri M.⁽²⁾, Aiello A.⁽²⁾, Dilena M.⁽²⁾, Dudine A.⁽³⁾, Menegon D.⁽³⁾, Gams M.⁽⁴⁾, Gostič S.⁽⁵⁾, Hafner R.⁽⁶⁾, Peršolja I.⁽⁶⁾

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Executive design documents concerning the interventions on the pilot buildings

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1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 3.4 of the PRO-SIS project, titled “Assessment of the seismic vulnerability of the pilot buildings”.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extensive experimental campaign. The strengthening method developed is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced with fibre-based composite materials. The main advantage of this system is that it can be applied to only one side of the wall, making it much more convenient for residents and businesses. As construction work can be carried out only on the exterior of the building, people and their belongings do not have to be relocated, and business activity does not have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the interior (or exterior, when interior application is preferred). The strengthening method stands out due to its proven effectiveness in tests on structural components and a full-scale pilot building.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for designing and applying these strategies. To this end, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated against the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide designers with robust strategies for designing the proposed systems, as well as instructions for design in commonly used commercial structural design programmes.

REPORT 3.3 [1] summarized the results concerning the assessment of the seismic vulnerability of the pilot buildings in their unreinforced configuration. This REPORT 3.4 refers to the strengthened configuration.

2. The building of ATER in Udine strengthened with CRM

2.1. General information

2.1.1. *Description of the structure*

The building has a rectangular floor plan measuring approximately 34.00 m x 9.45 m in plan view and consists of a basement, three floors above ground and an attic accessible for maintenance purposes only. The height at the ridge is approximately 12.60 m above ground level.

The vertical load-bearing elements consist of: (i) in the basement, unreinforced concrete walls with a thickness of 0.30 or 0.40 m; (ii) on the upper floors, solid brick and lime mortar walls with a thickness (unfinished, without plaster) of 0.25 and 0.38 m, respectively.

2.1.2. *Reference Standard Codes*

The dimensioning, verification and determination of the actions on the structure are carried out in compliance with Ministerial Decree 17/01/18 - Update of the "Technical Standards for Construction", appropriately completed and supplemented in some parts by:

- Circular no. 7/C.S.LL.PP, January 21, 2019, Instructions for the application of the Update of the "Technical Standards for Construction" referred to in Ministerial Decree 19 January 2018.
- CNR-DT 215/2018, Guide for the Design and Construction of Externally Bonded Fibre Reinforced Inorganic Matrix Systems for Strengthening Existing Structures.

2.2. Parameters of existing materials

This section summarises the characteristics of the existing materials used in both the calculation programme and the checks. For the assessment of the generic characteristic of strength or design deformation, reference is made to a level of knowledge LC2, which corresponds to a confidence factor value of $FC = 1.20$. This level was achieved because the information collected (see PRO-SIS Report 3.2 [2]) provided adequate knowledge of the geometry of the structure, the construction details and the mechanical characteristics of the materials:

Geometry: the geometry of the structure was obtained from an accurate survey of the entire building in all its parts;

Construction details: the construction details were obtained from an extensive in-situ verification of the connections between the walls and from a careful analysis of the masonry texture;

Material properties: information on the mechanical characteristics of the materials was obtained from extensive in-situ tests. The number of tests was determined taking into account the homogeneity characteristics of the various types of structures.

2.2.1. Mechanical properties of existing masonry

The main values of the material properties used in the numerical analyses are summarised below.

Type of masonry: solid bricks and lime mortar

The mechanical characteristics were determined with reference to the values reported in Table C8.5.I of Circular No. 7, January 21, 2019, for the type "solid brick and lime mortar masonry". The level of knowledge achieved through surveys of the building, concerning the geometry of the elements, construction details and material characteristics, is LC2. The mean values of the range in Table C8.5.I were considered for the normal and tangential moduli of elasticity; the mean compressive strength obtained from the flat jack tests was considered.

The following values are therefore chosen for the mechanical and physical characteristics of solid brick masonry:

Mean compressive strength:	$f_m = 2.012 \text{ MPa};$
Mean shear strength, with diagonal tensile failure:	$\tau_0 = 0.045 \text{ MPa};$
Mean shear strength, with "ladder" cracking:	$f_{v0} = 0.1124 \text{ MPa};$
Young's modulus of elasticity:	$E = 1500 \text{ MPa};$
Tangential modulus of elasticity:	$G = 500 \text{ MPa};$
Weight per unit volume:	$w = 18.0 \text{ kN/m}^3.$

To obtain the design strength values, the above quantities must be divided by the partial safety factor (γ_M) and the confidence factor $FC = 1.20$, that is:

Design compressive strength:	$f_{m,d} = 1.677 \text{ MPa};$
Design shear strength, with diagonal tensile failure:	$\tau_{0,d} = 0.0375 \text{ MPa};$
Design shear strength, with "ladder" cracking:	$f_{v0,d} = 0.0937 \text{ MPa}.$

Table 2.1 Reference values for mechanical parameters (minimum and maximum) and average specific weight for different types of masonry (Circular 2019, Table C8.5.I).

Tipologia di muratura	f	τ_0	f_{v0}	E	G	w
	(N/mm ²)	(kN/m ³)				
	min-max	min-max		min-max	min-max	
Muratura in pietrame disordinata (ciottoli, pietre erratiche e irregolari)	1,0-2,0	0,018-0,032	-	690-1050	230-350	19
Muratura a conci sbazzati, con paramenti di spessore disomogeneo (*)	2,0	0,035-0,051	-	1020-1440	340-480	20
Muratura in pietre a spacco con buona tessitura	2,6-3,8	0,056-0,074	-	1500-1980	500-660	21
Muratura irregolare di pietra tenera (tufo, calcarenite, ecc.,)	1,4-2,2	0,028-0,042	-	900-1260	300-420	13 + 16(**)
Muratura a conci regolari di pietra tenera (tufo, calcarenite, ecc.,) (**)	2,0-3,2	0,04-0,08	0,10-0,19	1200-1620	400-500	
Muratura a blocchi lapidei squadati	5,8-8,2	0,09-0,12	0,18-0,28	2400-3300	800-1100	22
Muratura in mattoni pieni e malta di calce (***)	2,6-4,3	0,05-0,13	0,13-0,27	1200-1800	400-600	18
Muratura in mattoni semipieni con malta cementizia (es.: doppio UNI foratura $\leq 40\%$)	5,0-8,0	0,08-0,17	0,20-0,36	3500-5600	875-1400	15

2.2.2. Characteristics of the new materials used for the strengthening intervention:

Preformed GFRP mesh

mesh:	66x66 mm;
number of wires each meter:	15;
mean tensile force of the wire:	$N_m = 4.96$ kN;
characteristic tensile force of the wire:	$N_k = 4.23$ kN;
nominal fibre area of the wire:	$A_w = 8.90$ mm ² ;
nominal fibre area of the fibre:	$A_f = 3.60$ mm ² ;
characteristic strength of the fibre:	$f_{fk} = 1175$ MPa;
Young's modulus of the wire:	$E_w = 31370$ MPa;
Young's modulus of the fibre:	$E_f = 77553$ MPa;
conventional strain limit of the fibre (end zones):	$\epsilon_{lim, conv} = 1.52\%$;
conventional strain limit of the fibre (intermediate zones):	$\epsilon_{lim, conv}(\alpha) = 1.21\%$;
Equivalent stiffness of the fibre:	$t_f = 0.0545$ mm;
CE certified about EAD 340392-00-0104.	

Preformed gfrp angular mesh

mesh:	66x66 mm;
number of wires each meter:	15;
mean tensile force of the wire:	$N_m = 4.96$ kN;
characteristic tensile force of the wire:	$N_k = 4.23$ kN;
nominal fibre area of the wire:	$A_w = 8.90$ mm ² ;
nominal fibre area of the fibre:	$A_f = 3.60$ mm ² ;

characteristic strength of the fibre:	$f_{fk} = 1175 \text{ MPa};$
Young's modulus of the wire:	$E_w = 31370 \text{ MPa};$
Young's modulus of the fibre:	$E_f = 77553 \text{ MPa};$
conventional strain limit of the fibre (end zones):	$\epsilon_{lim, conv} = 1.52\%;$
conventional strain limit of the fibre (intermediate zones):	$\epsilon_{lim, conv}(\alpha) = 1.21\%;$
Equivalent stiffness of the fibre:	$t_f = 0.0545 \text{ mm};$
side dimension:	30 cm;
CE certified about EAD 340392-00-0104.	

Preformed GFRP "L" shape connector

minimum section:	7x10 cm;
characteristic tensile force:	380 MPa;
nominal fiber area:	32.4 mm ² .

Anchor resin

type of resin:	vinylestere;
cleaning the holes with compressed air.	

Stainless steel AISI 316

characteristic yield strength:	$f_{yk} \geq 235 \text{ MPa};$
characteristic ultimate strength:	$f_{tk} \geq 500 \text{ MPa}.$

Bars and nuts class A4-7

characteristic yield strength:	$f_{yb} \geq 450 \text{ MPa};$
characteristic ultimate strength:	$f_{tb} \geq 700 \text{ MPa}.$

Lime based mortar M10

compressive strength - 28 days:	10 MPa;
Young's modulus:	10000 MPa;
thickness of the plaster:	30 mm;
qualified by EN 998-2.	

Cementitious based mortar M25

compressive strength - 28 days:	25 MPa;
qualified by EN 998-2.	

2.3. Actions on structures

Below are all the actions considered to act on the structure, which will then be included in the numerical model for determining the internal forces and displacements.

2.3.1. *Snow loads*

The snow load on roofs is given by the following expression:

$$q_s = \mu_i \times q_{sk} \times C_E \times C_t$$

where:

q_{sk}	characteristic value of snow on the ground at Site I ($a_s < 200\text{m}$)	1.50	kN/m ²
C_E	exposure coefficient	1.0	
C_t	thermal coefficient	1.0	
μ_i	roof slope $\alpha = 22^\circ < 30^\circ$, μ_i	0.80	

Snow load on the roof		1.20	kN/m²
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2.3.2. *Dead loads*

Roof (slope = 30%)

Material		Weight	
1 – Roof tiles		0.70	kN/m ²
2 – Sand and cement screed	(22.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 3 cm)	0.66	kN/m ²
3 – Brick floor joists	(dim. 25x20 cm, i = 60 cm)	0.46	kN/m ²
4 – Hollow clay bricks	(thickness 4 cm)	0.23	kN/m ²
Dead structural load G1	(3+4)	0.69	kN/m ²
Permanent bearing load G2	(1+2)	1.36	kN/m ²
Snow load Qs		1.20	kN/m ²

Attic

Material		Weight	
1 - Brick floor joists	(dim 25x20 cm, i = 90 cm)	0.31	kN/m ²
2 - Hollow clay bricks	(thickness 4 cm)	0.29	kN/m ²
3 - Plaster	(20.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 1 cm)	0.20	kN/m ²
Dead structural load G1	(1+2)	0.59	kN/m ²
Permanent bearing load G2	(3)	0.20	kN/m ²
Live load Qvar	(Cat. H - maintenance)	0.50	kN/m ²

Reinforced brick floor slab - typical floor, living area

Material		Weight	
1 - Tiled pavement	(24.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 1 cm)	0.24	kN/m ²
2 - Sand and cement screed	(22.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 4 cm)	0.88	kN/m ²
3 - Type SAP floor	(height h = 12+4 cm)	2.06	kN/m ²
4 - Plaster	(20.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 1 cm)	0.20	kN/m ²
5 - Partition walls		1.35	kN/m ²
Dead structural load G1	(3)	2.06	kN/m ²
Permanent bearing load G2	(1+2+4+5)	2.67	kN/m ²
Live load Qvar	(Cat. A - residential)	2.00	kN/m ²

Reinforced brick floor slab - typical floor, bedroom area

Material		Weight	
1 - Timber planking	(5.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 2.5 cm)	0.13	kN/m ²
2 - Sand and cement screed	(22.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 4 cm)	0.88	kN/m ²
3 - Type SAP floor	(height h = 12+4 cm)	2.06	kN/m ²
4 - Plaster	(20.0 kN/m ³ , thickness 1 cm)	0.20	kN/m ²
5 - Partition walls		1.30	kN/m ²
Dead structural load G1	(3)	2.06	kN/m ²
Permanent bearing load G2	(1+2+4+5)	2.51	kN/m ²
Live load Qvar	(Cat. A - residential)	2.00	kN/m ²

Stairs - landing slabs

Material		Weight	
1 - Landing/ramp slabs	(weighted average value)	3.90	kN/m ²
Carico variabile Qvar	(Categoria A)	4.00	kN/m ²

2.3.3. Seismic Parameters, Structural Factor, and Response Spectra

For the definition of the design seismic forces, the following characteristics are assumed for the structures in question:

- Site location: Via Flambro n. 8, Municipality of Udine (UD);
- Coordinates: Latitude 46.04601°, Longitude 13.22208°;
- Design life of the building, VN = 50 years;
- Use class of the building. II, CU = 1.0;
- Reference life of the building; VR = CU * VN = 50 years;

Fig. 2.1 Image from Google Maps

For the site under investigation, in relation to the considered limit states (i.e., for each of the probabilities of exceeding in the reference period PVR), the shape of the response spectrum is governed by the values of the following site-specific parameters for a rigid horizontal reference site:

- a_g Maximum horizontal ground acceleration;
- F_0 Maximum value of the spectral amplification factor in horizontal acceleration;
- T_{c^*} Starting period of the constant velocity segment of the spectrum in horizontal acceleration.

The following seismic parameters assumed for the considered limit states in the analysis of the subject structure are presented below:

Limit State	TR [years]	PVR [%]	a_g/g	F_0	T_{c^*} [s]
SLD	50	63	0.0719	2.47	0.26
SLV	475	10	0.2005	2.45	0.33

Soil Category

Based on the stratigraphic profile of the ground, a soil in the category B is assumed for this site, "Soft rocks and very dense granular deposits or very consistent fine-grained soils, characterized by an improvement in mechanical properties with depth and $V_{s,30}$ values ranging from 360 m/s to 800 m/s."

The topographic conditions of the site lead to assuming a topographic category T1, "Flat surface, slopes and isolated elevations with average inclination $\leq 15^\circ$ ".

The coefficients S_s and C_c are determined with reference to the chosen categories and the seismic parameters specific to the considered site.

Limit State	SS	St	$S = S_S \cdot S_t$	CC	TB [s]	TC [s]	TD [s]
SLD	1.20	1.00	1.20	1.440	0.125	0.374	1.888
SLV	1.20	1.00	1.20	1.373	0.151	0.453	2.402

Fig. 2.2. Elastic response spectra for SLV and SLD.

2.4. Updated numerical model of the building

2.4.1. Modelling with the Midas Gen software

For seismic assessment, a global push-over analysis of the building (non-linear static analysis) was carried out using the Midas Gen 2025 software (v.1.2).

The structural analysis was carried out in accordance with the National Standard Code (NTC 2018), adopting the equivalent frame modelling approach (Fig. 2.3), where the walls are considered composed of distinct macro-elements: the piers and spandrels. The structure was modelled as a three-dimensional frame of vertical and horizontal beam elements, representing deformable walls and bands, arranged along their principal axes and having their actual cross-section. The wall elements and bands were connected through rigid nodes located in segments of wall that are typically less susceptible to seismic damage.

Each vertical element was fixed at the base, and the effective deformation length was evaluated using the approach proposed in [6], see Fig. 2.4. The effective deformation length of the spandrels was assumed to be equal to the width of the adjacent opening. The analyses were conducted considering halved stiffness values (cracked stiffness). A diaphragm constraint was introduced along the horizontal levels of each floor and roof, allowing for the redistribution of seismic forces among the walls in proportion to their stiffness.

The loads have been introduced with their characteristic values as distributed actions on the floors and/or linearly on the beams (dead and live loads), see Fig. 2.5. The software automatically estimates the self-weight of the structural elements and of the seismic masses (considering both the loads defined by the user and the self-weight of the elements).

Fig. 2.3. Isometric view of the building structural walls (top) and equivalent frame model (bottom).

Fig. 2.4. Rule for determining the effective deformation length of the wall elements proposed in Dolce.

Fig. 2.5. Distributed loads reported acting on bond beams or spandrels.

The nonlinear response of the structure was concentrated in plastic hinges located in certain sections of the elements. In particular, the hinges at the ends of the deformable elements consider the in-plane flexural behaviour, whereas the shear response is concentrated in a central plastic hinge.

For unreinforced masonry, the behaviour of wall elements was assumed to be linear - perfectly plastic; the ultimate displacement capacities were assumed in line with the guidelines provided in Circular 21.01.2019 n. 7/C.S.LL.PP. The resistance and deformation capacities of the plastic hinges are summarised below:

Reinforced masonry	Shear failure	Bending failure
Piers	$V_P = b_P \cdot t_P \cdot \frac{1.5\tau_0}{\alpha} \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_0}{1.5\tau_0}}$ $\delta_u = 0.5 \%$	$M_P = \frac{\sigma_0 \cdot b_P^2 \cdot t_P}{2} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_0}{0.85 \cdot f_c}\right)$ $\delta_u = 1.0 \%$
Spandrels	$V_{S(R)} = b_S \cdot t_S \cdot \frac{1.5\tau_{0(R)}}{\alpha}$ $\delta_u = 0.5 \%$	$M_S = \frac{H \cdot b_S}{2} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{H}{0.85 \cdot f_{c,h} \cdot b_S \cdot t_S}\right)$ $\delta_u = 1.0 \%$

where:

- l_p, b_p, t_p height, width, and thickness of the pier;
- l_s, b_s, t_s height, width, and thickness of the spandrel;
- $\alpha = l/b$, with $1.0 \leq \alpha \leq 1.5$;
- σ_0 uniform normal stress on the cross-section;
- τ_0 shear strength of the masonry;
- $f_c, f_{c,h}$ compressive strength in vertical and horizontal directions, respectively, where $f_{c,h} = 0.5 f_c$;
- H minimum value between the tensile strength of the tie (bond beams or L-shaped metallic rods) and $0.4 \cdot f_{c,h} \cdot b_s \cdot t_s$.

In the ATER building spandrels have no horizontal ties. To take into account of the, even small, bending resistance due to the interaction between adjacent blocks at the spandrel ends, the approach described in PRO-SIS Report 1.4 [3] has been adopted. Based on the provided hinges properties, the software automatically calculates the lateral strength and displacement capacities of masonry piers and spandrels; the axial stress intensity is automatically updated at each analysis step. The software considers the mean axial stress in the central cross-section of each element to determine the resistance of hinges.

Currently, the software does not include an automatic procedure to account for the CRM contribution. As already discussed in [4], for CRM strengthened masonry, the user shall “force” the software by providing “fictitious” equivalent masonry properties, to account also for the CRM reinforcement contribution. In fact, the software does not allow to modify the correlations for the resistance estimation, but just the masonry material parameters and plastic hinges drift limits.

For CRM strengthened elements (both piers and spandrels), the “spandrel element type” shall be selected in the software and equivalent material parameters values $\tau_{0,eq}$ (masonry shear strength) and $H_{p,eq}$ must be set, according to Eqs (3.1) and (3.2)

$$\tau_{0,eq} = -\frac{\sigma_0}{3} + \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_0^2}{9} + \left(\frac{\beta \cdot V_{d(CRM)}}{1.5 \cdot b \cdot t}\right)^2} \quad (3.1)$$

$$H_{p,eq} = \frac{2 \cdot M_{(CRM)}}{b} \quad (3.2)$$

where:

- $V_{d(CRM)}$ Resistance of the CRM strengthened masonry element in shear (related to the in-plane diagonal cracking mechanism)
- M_{CRM} Resistance of the CRM strengthened masonry element in bending (related to the in-plane bending mechanism)

The values of $V_{d(CRM)}$ and M_{CRM} shall be calculated analytically by the user, applying the correlations provided in the “PRO-SIS” Guidelines - Report 2.4 [4] for CRM, in accordance with the CNR-DT 215/2018 guidelines for strengthening with FRCM. Note also that the masonry

compressive strength shall be set fictitiously to a high value (e.g. 1000 MPa). For spandrel elements, it is assumed $\sigma_0 = 0$ in Eq. (3.1). Also increased ultimate drift values must be assigned to CRM strengthened masonry elements.

The deformation in the piers, due to bending and shear failure mechanisms, was conservatively assumed to be 1.6% and 0.8% respectively, as specified by the NTC 2018 standard for reinforced masonry buildings. For spandrels, the reinforcement allows elements with tensile strength (the glass fibres) to be coupled to the masonry spandrels. Based on experimental tests and numerical studies on brick walls of the same type, the limit displacement was set, again conservatively at 2.0% for the flexural strength and 1.5% for the shear strength.

In the modelling of either L or T-intersecting walls, one or more links connecting the longitudinal axes have been inserted at each floor level. Following the same procedure outlined in Report 3.3 [1], an internal beam release has been introduced at the intersection node of the connecting beams to prevent the transfer of torsional effects, while the flexural stiffness has been calibrated on the effective sliding between the orthogonal walls. Therefore, in the connecting beams, with infinite flexural stiffness, suitable shear hinges were assigned with resistance equal to the limit force and subsequent sudden reduction at 40%, to take into account the cracking between the masonry units, Fig. 2.6. The limit force F_{lim} is equal to 29.8 kN or 45.3 kN for walls with height 3.18 m and thickness 0.25 m or 0.38 m, respectively.

Fig. 2.6. Plastic shear hinge applied to the connecting link at the top of the coupled piers on each floor.

2.4.2. Numerical model data

This section provides tables with the main data defining the geometry of the numerical model of the building, the elements used, the mechanical properties of the materials, the vertical loads applied.

2.4.2.1. Mechanical properties of materials

ID	Name	Description	E [MPa]	G [MPa]	y [kN/m ³]
7	ID7	Full brick masonry + plaster weight	1500	500	20.4
17	ID7-s25	Reinforced masonry wall, thickness 0.25 m	2700	900	20.4
27	ID7-s38	Reinforced masonry wall, thickness 0.38 m	2290	763	20.4

996	NoMass	Used in auxiliary elements bearing loads	28000	11667	0.0
998	Cls_Esist	Concrete	28000	11667	25.0
999	Rigido	Used in the rigid elements connecting spandrels and piers	750000	375000	0.0

2.4.2.2. Nodes

The number of nodes and coordinates are unchanged compared to the building in its unreinforced configuration. Refer to the table in PRO-SIS Report 3.3 [1] for further details.

First story

Second story

Third story

2.4.2.3. Sections

Compared to the model of the building in its unstrengthened configuration, the Sections ID, Name, Area section, remain unchanged. Refer to PRO-SIS Report 3.3 [1] for further details.

2.4.2.4. Elements

There are no variations with respect to the unreinforced configuration, see Section 2.4.2.4 for more details.

First story

Second story

Third story

2.4.2.5. Plastic hinges

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
101	Beam	101-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
101	Beam	101-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
101	Beam	101-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
102	Beam	102-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
102	Beam	102-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
102	Beam	102-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
103	Beam	103-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
103	Beam	103-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
103	Beam	103-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
104	Beam	104-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
104	Beam	104-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
104	Beam	104-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
105	Beam	105-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
105	Beam	105-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
105	Beam	105-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
106	Beam	106-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
106	Beam	106-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
106	Beam	106-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
107	Beam	107-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
107	Beam	107-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
107	Beam	107-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
108	Beam	108-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
108	Beam	108-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
108	Beam	108-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
109	Beam	109-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
109	Beam	109-M	Spandrel	My	I-End

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
109	Beam	109-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
111	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
111	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
111	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
114	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
114	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
114	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
117	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
117	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
117	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
120	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
120	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
120	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
122	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
122	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
122	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
123	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
123	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
123	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
125	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
125	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
125	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
127	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
127	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
127	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
128	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
128	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
128	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
129	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
129	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
129	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
131	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
131	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
131	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
133	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
133	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
133	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
134	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
134	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
134	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
135	Beam	135-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
135	Beam	135-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
135	Beam	135-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
136	Beam	136-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
136	Beam	136-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
136	Beam	136-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
137	Beam	137-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
137	Beam	137-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
137	Beam	137-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
138	Beam	138-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
138	Beam	138-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
138	Beam	138-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
139	Beam	139-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
139	Beam	139-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
139	Beam	139-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
140	Beam	140-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
140	Beam	140-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
140	Beam	140-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
141	Beam	141-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
141	Beam	141-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
141	Beam	141-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
142	Beam	142-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
142	Beam	142-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
142	Beam	142-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
143	Beam	143-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
143	Beam	143-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
143	Beam	143-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
144	Beam	144-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
144	Beam	144-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
144	Beam	144-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
145	Beam	145-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
145	Beam	145-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
145	Beam	145-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
146	Beam	146-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
146	Beam	146-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
146	Beam	146-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
147	Beam	147-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
147	Beam	147-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
147	Beam	147-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
148	Beam	148-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
148	Beam	148-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
148	Beam	148-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
150	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	Fz	Center
150	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	My	I-End
150	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	My	J-End

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
151	Beam	151-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
151	Beam	151-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
151	Beam	151-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
152	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	Fz	Center
152	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	My	I-End
152	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	My	J-End
153	Beam	153-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
153	Beam	153-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
153	Beam	153-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
155	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	Fz	Center
155	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	My	I-End
155	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	My	J-End
156	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	Fz	Center
156	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	My	I-End
156	Beam	ID7-M2	Pier	My	J-End
157	Beam	157-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
157	Beam	157-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
157	Beam	157-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
158	Beam	158-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
158	Beam	158-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
158	Beam	158-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
201	Beam	201-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
201	Beam	201-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
201	Beam	201-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
202	Beam	202-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
202	Beam	202-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
202	Beam	202-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
203	Beam	203-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
203	Beam	203-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
203	Beam	203-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
204	Beam	204-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
204	Beam	204-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
204	Beam	204-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
205	Beam	205-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
205	Beam	205-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
205	Beam	205-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
206	Beam	206-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
206	Beam	206-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
206	Beam	206-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
207	Beam	207-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
207	Beam	207-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
207	Beam	207-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
208	Beam	208-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
208	Beam	208-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
208	Beam	208-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
209	Beam	209-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
209	Beam	209-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
209	Beam	209-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
211	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
211	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
211	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
214	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
214	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
214	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
217	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
217	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
217	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
220	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
220	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
220	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
222	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
222	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
222	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
223	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
223	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
223	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
225	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
225	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
225	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
227	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
227	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
227	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
228	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
228	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
228	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
229	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
229	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
229	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
231	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
231	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
231	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
233	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
233	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
233	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
234	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
234	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
234	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
235	Beam	235-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
235	Beam	235-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
235	Beam	235-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
236	Beam	236-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
236	Beam	236-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
236	Beam	236-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
237	Beam	237-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
237	Beam	237-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
237	Beam	237-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
238	Beam	238-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
238	Beam	238-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
238	Beam	238-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
239	Beam	239-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
239	Beam	239-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
239	Beam	239-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
240	Beam	240-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
240	Beam	240-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
240	Beam	240-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
241	Beam	241-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
241	Beam	241-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
241	Beam	241-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
242	Beam	242-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
242	Beam	242-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
242	Beam	242-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
243	Beam	243-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
243	Beam	243-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
243	Beam	243-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
244	Beam	244-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
244	Beam	244-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
244	Beam	244-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
245	Beam	245-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
245	Beam	245-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
245	Beam	245-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
246	Beam	246-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
246	Beam	246-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
246	Beam	246-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
247	Beam	247-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
247	Beam	247-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
247	Beam	247-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
248	Beam	248-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
248	Beam	248-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
248	Beam	248-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
250	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
250	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
250	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
251	Beam	251-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
251	Beam	251-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
251	Beam	251-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
252	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
252	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
252	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
253	Beam	253-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
253	Beam	253-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
253	Beam	253-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
255	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
255	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
255	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
256	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
256	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
256	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
257	Beam	257-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
257	Beam	257-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
257	Beam	257-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
258	Beam	258-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
258	Beam	258-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
258	Beam	258-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
301	Beam	301-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
301	Beam	301-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
301	Beam	301-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
302	Beam	302-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
302	Beam	302-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
302	Beam	302-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
303	Beam	303-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
303	Beam	303-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
303	Beam	303-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
304	Beam	304-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
304	Beam	304-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
304	Beam	304-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
305	Beam	305-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
305	Beam	305-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
305	Beam	305-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
306	Beam	306-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
306	Beam	306-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
306	Beam	306-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
307	Beam	307-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
307	Beam	307-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
307	Beam	307-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
308	Beam	308-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
308	Beam	308-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
308	Beam	308-M	Spandrel	My	J-End

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
309	Beam	309-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
309	Beam	309-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
309	Beam	309-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
311	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
311	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
311	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
314	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
314	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
314	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
317	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
317	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
317	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
320	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
320	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
320	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
322	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
322	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
322	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
323	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
323	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
323	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
325	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
325	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
325	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
327	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
327	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
327	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
328	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
328	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
328	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
329	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
329	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
329	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
331	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
331	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
331	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
333	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
333	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
333	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
334	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
334	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
334	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
335	Beam	335-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
335	Beam	335-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
335	Beam	335-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
336	Beam	336-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
336	Beam	336-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
336	Beam	336-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
337	Beam	337-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
337	Beam	337-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
337	Beam	337-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
338	Beam	338-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
338	Beam	338-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
338	Beam	338-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
338	Beam	338-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
338	Beam	338-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
339	Beam	339-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
339	Beam	339-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
339	Beam	339-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
340	Beam	340-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
340	Beam	340-M	Spandrel	My	I-End

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
340	Beam	340-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
341	Beam	341-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
341	Beam	341-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
341	Beam	341-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
342	Beam	342-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
342	Beam	342-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
342	Beam	342-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
343	Beam	343-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
343	Beam	343-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
343	Beam	343-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
344	Beam	344-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
344	Beam	344-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
344	Beam	344-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
344	Beam	344-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
345	Beam	345-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
345	Beam	345-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
345	Beam	345-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
346	Beam	346-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
346	Beam	346-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
346	Beam	346-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
347	Beam	347-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
347	Beam	347-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
347	Beam	347-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
348	Beam	348-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
348	Beam	348-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
348	Beam	348-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
350	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
350	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
350	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
351	Beam	351-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
351	Beam	351-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
351	Beam	351-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
352	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
352	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
352	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
353	Beam	353-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
353	Beam	353-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
353	Beam	353-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
355	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
355	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
355	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
356	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	Fz	Center
356	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	I-End
356	Beam	ID7-M	Pier	My	J-End
357	Beam	357-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
357	Beam	357-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
357	Beam	357-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
358	Beam	358-M	Spandrel	Fz	Center
358	Beam	358-M	Spandrel	My	I-End
358	Beam	358-M	Spandrel	My	J-End
585	Beam	585-F	Spandrel	Fz	Center
585	Beam	585-F	Spandrel	My	I-End
585	Beam	585-F	Spandrel	My	J-End
588	Beam	588-F	Spandrel	Fz	Center
588	Beam	588-F	Spandrel	My	I-End
588	Beam	588-F	Spandrel	My	J-End
591	Beam	591-F	Spandrel	Fz	Center
591	Beam	591-F	Spandrel	My	I-End
591	Beam	591-F	Spandrel	My	J-End
602	Beam	602-F	Spandrel	Fz	Center

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
602	Beam	602-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
602	Beam	602-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
605	Beam	605-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
605	Beam	605-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
605	Beam	605-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
608	Beam	608-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
608	Beam	608-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
608	Beam	608-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
618	Beam	618-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
618	Beam	618-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
618	Beam	618-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
621	Beam	621-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
621	Beam	621-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
621	Beam	621-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
624	Beam	624-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
624	Beam	624-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
624	Beam	624-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
627	Beam	627-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
627	Beam	627-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
627	Beam	627-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
630	Beam	630-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
630	Beam	630-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
630	Beam	630-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
633	Beam	633-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
633	Beam	633-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
633	Beam	633-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
636	Beam	636-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
636	Beam	636-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
636	Beam	636-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
639	Beam	639-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
639	Beam	639-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
639	Beam	639-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
642	Beam	642-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
642	Beam	642-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
642	Beam	642-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
645	Beam	645-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
645	Beam	645-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
645	Beam	645-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
650	Beam	650-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
650	Beam	650-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
650	Beam	650-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
653	Beam	653-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
653	Beam	653-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
653	Beam	653-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
656	Beam	656-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
656	Beam	656-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
656	Beam	656-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
659	Beam	659-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
659	Beam	659-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
659	Beam	659-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
662	Beam	662-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
662	Beam	662-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
662	Beam	662-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
665	Beam	665-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
665	Beam	665-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
665	Beam	665-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
668	Beam	668-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
668	Beam	668-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
668	Beam	668-F	Spandrel My	J-End	

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
671	Beam	671-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
671	Beam	671-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
671	Beam	671-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
674	Beam	674-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
674	Beam	674-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
674	Beam	674-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
677	Beam	677-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
677	Beam	677-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
677	Beam	677-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
682	Beam	682-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
682	Beam	682-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
682	Beam	682-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
685	Beam	685-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
685	Beam	685-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
685	Beam	685-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
688	Beam	688-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
688	Beam	688-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
688	Beam	688-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
691	Beam	691-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
691	Beam	691-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
691	Beam	691-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
694	Beam	694-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
694	Beam	694-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
694	Beam	694-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
697	Beam	697-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
697	Beam	697-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
697	Beam	697-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
700	Beam	700-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
700	Beam	700-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
700	Beam	700-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
703	Beam	703-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
703	Beam	703-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
703	Beam	703-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
706	Beam	706-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
706	Beam	706-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
706	Beam	706-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
709	Beam	709-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
709	Beam	709-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
709	Beam	709-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
754	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
756	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
756	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
756	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
759	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
759	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
759	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
762	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
762	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
762	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
767	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
767	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
767	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
770	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
770	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
770	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
773	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
773	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
773	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
776	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
776	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
776	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
779	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
779	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
779	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
782	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
782	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
782	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
787	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
787	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
787	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
790	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
790	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
790	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
793	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
793	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
793	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
795	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
796	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
798	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
798	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
798	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
801	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
801	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
801	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
804	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
804	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
804	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
809	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
809	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
809	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
812	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
812	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
812	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
815	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
815	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
815	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
818	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
818	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
818	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
821	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
821	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
821	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
824	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
824	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
824	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
829	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
829	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
829	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
832	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
832	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
832	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
835	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
835	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
835	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
837	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
838	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
840	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
840	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
840	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
843	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
843	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
843	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
846	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
846	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
846	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
851	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
851	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
851	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
854	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
854	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
854	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
857	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
857	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
857	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
860	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
860	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
860	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
863	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
863	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
863	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
866	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
866	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
866	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
871	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
871	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
871	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
874	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
874	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
874	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
877	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
877	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
877	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
879	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
880	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel Fz	Center	
880	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel My	I-End	
880	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel My	J-End	
891	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel Fz	Center	
891	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel My	I-End	
891	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel My	J-End	
892	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel Fz	Center	
892	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	I-End	
892	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	J-End	
895	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel Fz	Center	
895	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	I-End	
895	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	J-End	
900	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel Fz	Center	
900	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	I-End	
900	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	J-End	
903	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel Fz	Center	
903	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	I-End	
903	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	J-End	
904	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel Fz	Center	
904	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	I-End	
904	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	J-End	
907	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel Fz	Center	
907	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	I-End	
907	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	J-End	

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
912	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel Fz	Center	
912	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	I-End	
912	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	J-End	
915	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel Fz	Center	
915	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	I-End	
915	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	J-End	
916	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel Fz	Center	
916	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel My	I-End	
916	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel My	J-End	
922	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel Fz	Center	
922	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	I-End	
922	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	J-End	
925	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel Fz	Center	
925	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	I-End	
925	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	J-End	
928	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel Fz	Center	
928	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	I-End	
928	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	J-End	
931	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel Fz	Center	
931	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	I-End	
931	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	J-End	
939	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel Fz	Center	
939	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel My	I-End	
939	Beam	ID7-F10	Spandrel My	J-End	
942	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel Fz	Center	
942	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	I-End	
942	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	J-End	
945	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel Fz	Center	
945	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	I-End	
945	Beam	ID7-F11	Spandrel My	J-End	
948	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel Fz	Center	
948	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	I-End	
948	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	J-End	
951	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel Fz	Center	
951	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	I-End	
951	Beam	ID7-F12	Spandrel My	J-End	
952	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel Fz	Center	
952	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	I-End	
952	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	J-End	
955	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel Fz	Center	
955	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	I-End	
955	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	J-End	
960	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel Fz	Center	
960	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	I-End	
960	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	J-End	
963	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel Fz	Center	
963	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	I-End	
963	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	J-End	
964	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel Fz	Center	
964	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	I-End	
964	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	J-End	
967	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel Fz	Center	
967	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	I-End	
967	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	J-End	
972	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel Fz	Center	
972	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	I-End	
972	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	J-End	
975	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel Fz	Center	
975	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	I-End	

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
975	Beam	ID7-F9	Spandrel My	J-End	
978	Beam	978-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
978	Beam	978-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
978	Beam	978-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
983	Beam	983-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
983	Beam	983-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
983	Beam	983-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
986	Beam	986-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
986	Beam	986-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
986	Beam	986-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
991	Beam	991-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
991	Beam	991-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
991	Beam	991-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
996	Beam	996-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
996	Beam	996-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
996	Beam	996-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
1001	Beam	1001-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1001	Beam	1001-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
1001	Beam	1001-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
1018	Beam	1018-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1018	Beam	1018-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
1018	Beam	1018-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
1023	Beam	1023-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1023	Beam	1023-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
1023	Beam	1023-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
1028	Beam	1028-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1028	Beam	1028-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
1028	Beam	1028-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
1031	Beam	1031-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1031	Beam	1031-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
1031	Beam	1031-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
1036	Beam	1036-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1036	Beam	1036-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
1036	Beam	1036-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
1039	Beam	1039-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1039	Beam	1039-F	Spandrel My	I-End	
1039	Beam	1039-F	Spandrel My	J-End	
1072	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1074	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1076	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1078	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1084	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1086	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1088	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1090	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1096	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1098	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1100	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1102	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1104	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1106	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1108	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1110	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1112	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1114	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1117	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1120	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1120	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
1120	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
1121	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1123	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1126	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1126	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
1126	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
1127	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1129	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1132	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1132	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
1132	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
1133	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1135	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1138	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1138	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
1138	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
1139	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1147	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1150	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1150	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
1150	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
1151	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1153	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1156	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1156	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
1156	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
1157	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1165	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1166	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1168	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1169	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1170	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1171	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1202	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1202	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
1202	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
1203	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1203	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
1203	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
1204	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1204	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
1204	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
1205	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1205	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
1205	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
1206	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1206	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
1206	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
1207	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1207	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
1207	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
1208	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1208	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
1208	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
1209	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1209	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
1209	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
1210	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1210	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
1210	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
1211	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1211	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
1211	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
1212	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1212	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	I-End	
1212	Beam	ID7-F6	Spandrel My	J-End	
1213	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1213	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	I-End	
1213	Beam	ID7-F7	Spandrel My	J-End	
1214	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1214	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
1214	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
1215	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1215	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
1215	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
1216	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1216	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
1216	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
1217	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1217	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
1217	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
1218	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1218	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
1218	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
1219	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1219	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	I-End	
1219	Beam	ID7-F8	Spandrel My	J-End	
1228	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1232	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1247	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1251	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1255	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1259	Beam	Link	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1262	Beam	1262-M	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1262	Beam	1262-M	Spandrel My	I-End	
1262	Beam	1262-M	Spandrel My	J-End	
1263	Beam	1263-M	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1263	Beam	1263-M	Spandrel My	I-End	
1263	Beam	1263-M	Spandrel My	J-End	
1264	Beam	1264-M	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1264	Beam	1264-M	Spandrel My	I-End	
1264	Beam	1264-M	Spandrel My	J-End	
1265	Beam	1265-M	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1265	Beam	1265-M	Spandrel My	I-End	
1265	Beam	1265-M	Spandrel My	J-End	
1266	Beam	1266-M	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1266	Beam	1266-M	Spandrel My	I-End	
1266	Beam	1266-M	Spandrel My	J-End	
1267	Beam	1267-M	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1267	Beam	1267-M	Spandrel My	I-End	
1267	Beam	1267-M	Spandrel My	J-End	
1268	Beam	1268-M	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1268	Beam	1268-M	Spandrel My	I-End	
1268	Beam	1268-M	Spandrel My	J-End	
1269	Beam	1269-M	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1269	Beam	1269-M	Spandrel My	I-End	
1269	Beam	1269-M	Spandrel My	J-End	
1312	Beam	1312-F	Spandrel Fz	Center	
1312	Beam	1312-F	Spandrel My	I-End	

Elem. No.	Elem. Type	Prop. Name	Defin.	DOF	Loc. / Num.
1312	Beam	1312-F	Spandrel	My	J-End
1317	Beam	1317-F	Spandrel	Fz	Center
1317	Beam	1317-F	Spandrel	My	I-End
1317	Beam	1317-F	Spandrel	My	J-End
1320	Beam	1320-F	Spandrel	Fz	Center
1320	Beam	1320-F	Spandrel	My	I-End
1320	Beam	1320-F	Spandrel	My	J-End
1322	Beam	1322-F	Spandrel	Fz	Center
1322	Beam	1322-F	Spandrel	My	I-End
1322	Beam	1322-F	Spandrel	My	J-End
1324	Beam	1324-F	Spandrel	Fz	Center
1324	Beam	1324-F	Spandrel	My	I-End
1324	Beam	1324-F	Spandrel	My	J-End
1326	Beam	1326-F	Spandrel	Fz	Center
1326	Beam	1326-F	Spandrel	My	I-End
1326	Beam	1326-F	Spandrel	My	J-End

2.4.3. Modal analysis

A modal analysis has been carried out to define the vibrating mode shapes of the structure and associate the percentage of the total mass excited by each mode. The results terms of frequency, period, percentage of participant mass, related to the first 9 modes are summarized in Table 2.2.

It is noted that, both in the longitudinal direction (mode 1, see Fig. 2.7) and in the transversal direction (mode 2, see Fig. 2.8), there is a fundamental translational mode that excites almost 64% and 66% of the mass, respectively. Mode 3 is torsional around the vertical axis, see Fig. 2.9. For the first 9 modes the mass participation ratio reaches almost 75% of the total mass.

On the other hand, the basement, built with concrete walls having limited openings, is at least an order of magnitude stiffer than the solid brick masonry walls on the upper floors. It is assumed, therefore, that during a seismic event, the basement will move rigidly with the ground.

Table 2.2 Modal analysis results in terms of frequency, period, percentage of modal participation mass

Mode	Frequency (Hz)	Period (s)	TRAN-X MASS(%)	SUM(%)	TRAN-Y MASS(%)	SUM(%)	ROTN-Z MASS(%)	SUM(%)
1	3.594	0.2783	63.8	63.8	0.0	0.0	1.1	1.1
2	3.979	0.2513	0.0	63.8	66.3	66.3	0.0	1.1
3	4.907	0.2038	1.2	65.0	0.0	66.3	66.2	67.4
4	10.609	0.0943	8.7	73.7	0.0	66.3	0.2	67.6
5	11.220	0.0891	0.0	73.7	7.9	74.2	0.0	67.6
6	13.418	0.0745	0.1	73.8	0.0	74.2	1.0	68.6
7	13.552	0.0738	0.0	73.8	0.5	74.7	0.0	68.6
8	13.963	0.0716	0.1	73.9	0.0	74.7	6.6	75.1
9	16.169	0.0618	0.0	73.9	0.0	74.7	0.0	75.1

midas Gen POST-PROCESSOR VIBRATION MODE	
FREQUENCY (CYCLE/SEC)	3.593799
NATURAL PERIOD (SEC)	0.278257
MPM(%)	
DX=	63.834515
DY=	0.000000
DZ=	0.000000
RX=	0.000000
RY=	19.958823
RZ=	1.124386
MODE 1	
MAX :	1601
MIN :	1
FILE :	RM-06A
UNIT :	kN,m
DATE :	12/19/2025
VIEW-DIRECTION	
X:	-0.612
Y:	-0.612
Z:	0.500

Fig. 2.7 First translational vibrating mode in the longitudinal direction (Mode 1): frequency 3.59 Hz; period 0.278 s; modal participation mass: 63.8%

midas Gen POST-PROCESSOR VIBRATION MODE	
FREQUENCY (CYCLE/SEC)	3.978614
NATURAL PERIOD (SEC)	0.251344
MPM(%)	
DX=	0.000000
DY=	66.307868
DZ=	0.000000
RX=	19.646187
RY=	0.000000
RZ=	0.000000
MODE 2	
MAX :	1696
MIN :	1
FILE :	RM-06A
UNIT :	kN,m
DATE :	12/19/2025
VIEW-DIRECTION	
X:	-0.612
Y:	-0.612
Z:	0.500

Fig. 2.8 First translational vibrating mode in the transversal direction (Mode 2): frequency 3.98 Hz; period 0.251 s; modal participation mass: 66.3%


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midas Gen
POST-PROCESSOR
VIBRATION MODE
-----
FREQUENCY
(CYCLE/SEC)
4.906806
NATURAL PERIOD
(SEC)
0.203799
MPM(%)
DX= 1.189149
DY= 0.000000
DZ= 0.000000
RX= 0.000000
RY= 0.288347
RZ= 66.226874

MODE 3
-----
MAX : 1672
MIN : 1
FILE: RM-06A
UNIT: kN,m
DATE: 12/19/2025
VIEW-DIRECTION
X:-0.612
Y:-0.612
Z: 0.500
    
```

Fig. 2.9 First torsional vibrating mode around the vertical axis: frequency 4.91 Hz; period 0.204 s.

A new modal analysis is carried out, neglecting the self-weight of the concrete walls and the additional loads on the lower floor. The results are listed in Table 2.3. Despite very slight variations in the values of the first frequencies (and corresponding modal shapes), the modal participation mass of the longitudinal (transverse) vibration mode reaches approximately 77% (80%). Considering a certain coupling with higher-order modes, it is reasonable to use non-linear static analysis. This analysis refers to a force distribution based on the first translational vibration mode, as well as a distribution proportional to the masses, to implicitly account for the effects of cracking under increasing stress.

Table 2.3 Modal analysis results in terms of frequency, period, percentage of modal participation mass neglecting the self-weight of the concrete walls and the additional loads on the basement floor.

Mode	Frequency	Period	TRAN-X		TRAN-Y		ROTN-Z	
	(Hz)	(s)	MASS(%)	SUM(%)	MASS(%)	SUM(%)	MASS(%)	SUM(%)
1	3.611	0.2769	76.6	76.6	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.3
2	3.998	0.2501	0.0	76.6	79.5	79.5	0.0	1.3
3	4.924	0.2031	1.3	78.0	0.0	79.5	78.3	79.6
4	10.662	0.0938	10.2	88.2	0.0	79.5	0.3	79.8
5	11.271	0.0887	0.0	88.2	9.2	88.7	0.0	79.8
6	13.426	0.0745	0.1	88.2	0.0	88.7	1.0	80.8
7	13.554	0.0738	0.0	88.2	0.6	89.3	0.0	80.8
8	11.329	0.0883	0.0	87.4	0.0	89.2	7.8	88.3
9	13.510	0.0740	0.0	87.4	0.0	89.2	0.0	88.3

2.5. Global analysis of the CRM strengthened structure

2.5.1. *Analysis characteristics*

The seismic assessment is conducted considering the load combination:

$$G_1 + G_2 + \psi_{21} \cdot Q_{k1} + \psi_{22} \cdot Q_{k2} + \dots$$

with:

- G_1, G_2 : structural and non-structural dead loads
- Q_k : live loads
- ψ_2 : reduction factor for live loads

The global building check was carried out following the "Method B", or capacity spectrum method (CSM), indicated in the Circular No. 617/C.S.LL.PP, January 21, 2019, considering a force distribution proportional to the fundamental vibration mode for both the principal directions, a force distribution proportional to the loads from the equivalent lateral force method (linear static analysis), a force distribution derived from a uniform acceleration trend along the height of the structure.

For the two principal distributions, an accidental eccentricity of the floor masses, with respect to their original position and orthogonally to the direction of seismic propagation, equal to 5% of the building footprint, was introduced.

The push-over analysis allows for constructing the capacity curve relative to the three load distributions, in the two directions with positive (+) and negative (-) force directions, and with positive and negative eccentricities (Table 2.4). From symmetry considerations with respect to the transverse plane passing through the centre of mass of the building, four pushover analyses for every force distribution are sufficient to satisfy the National Code requirements.

The analysis is continued until a reduction of the shear at the base by 15% from its peak value is observed. Thus, the maximum displacement at the top of the building generated by that force distribution is calculated. This displacement value is assumed as the ultimate value for the building.

Generally speaking, in the context of pushover analysis, the Capacity Spectrum Method is a procedure used to evaluate a building's seismic performance by directly comparing its structural capacity with the seismic demand of the site. The basic idea is the following: both the building's pushover curve and the design response spectrum are transformed into a common reference system and plotted in the Acceleration-Displacement Response Spectrum (ADRS).

Table 2.4. Load cases in the pushover analysis.

Load case	Direction	Force distribution	Description
LC01	X	seismic static	longitudinal positive direction, positive accidental eccentricity
LC02	Y	seismic static	transversal positive direction, positive accidental eccentricity
LC03	X	seismic static	longitudinal positive direction, negative accidental eccentricity
LC04	Y	seismic static	transversal negative direction, positive accidental eccentricity
LC05	X	mode shape	longitudinal positive direction, positive accidental eccentricity
LC06	Y	mode shape	transversal positive direction, positive accidental eccentricity
LC07	X	mode shape	longitudinal positive direction, negative accidental eccentricity
LC08	Y	mode shape	transversal negative direction, positive accidental eccentricity
LC09	X	uniform	longitudinal positive direction
LC10	Y	uniform	transversal positive direction
LC11	X	uniform	longitudinal negative direction
LC12	Y	uniform	transversal negative direction

The procedure starts from the standard pushover analysis, which provides the base shear-master node displacement curve of the building. This curve is then converted into an equivalent single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) system by determining the participating mass and the predominant mode shape. Using this equivalence, each point of the curve can be expressed as a pair of displacement and acceleration values, thus constructing the capacity spectrum—a direct representation of the building's resistance as a function of its global deformation.

At the same time, the site's demand spectrum is also transformed into the ADRS format. However, because buildings do not behave elastically beyond certain thresholds, the seismic demand must be reduced using an equivalent damping approach, meaning that the damping ratio increases as the structure moves into the nonlinear range.

The core of the method is the determination of the performance point, that is, the point where the capacity spectrum intersects the modified demand spectrum. This point represents the equilibrium between the structure's capacity and the seismic demand and provide an estimate of the displacement that the building is expected to reach during earthquake. Once the performance point is found in the equivalent system, its displacement is mapped back onto the real structural model to evaluate the behaviour of individual components.

According to the Circular 2019, the method for reducing the response spectrum curve of the equivalent SDOF system for increased damping is as follows: for any limit states LS1, LS2 \equiv Limit State of Damage (SLD), LS3 \equiv Limit State of Life Safety (SLV), LS4 on the pushover curve:

1. A bilinearization is done on the ADRS curve such that the slope of the initial portion of the bilinear curve is same as the initial tangent stiffness of the Pushover curve, and the area under the Pushover curve is equal to that under the bilinear curve.

2. From the points (d_{LSi}, F_{LSi}) and (d_y, F_y) , $i = 1, \dots, 4$, the equivalent viscous damping $\xi_{eq,i}$, expressed in percent, is given by:

$$\xi_{eq,i} = k \frac{63.7(F_y d_{LSi} - F_{LSi} d_y)}{F_{LSi} d_{LSi}} + 5,$$

where the coefficient k takes into account the dissipative capacity of the structure, and particularly the hysteresis cycle. For structures with low dissipative capacity (high pinching and reduced area), as in this case study, $k = 0.33$ was assumed.

For comparison, a different approach was followed: equivalent viscous damping may be defined for each LSi as a function of the displacement by the relation proposed in (Calvi, 1999), (Priestley et al., 2007),

$$\xi_{eq,i} = \xi_0 + \xi_H \left[1 - \left(\frac{d_y}{d_{LSi}} \right)^\zeta \right],$$

where: ξ_0 is the initial damping (usually assumed equal to 5%), ξ_H is the maximum hysteretic damping (15%) and ζ is a free parameter (ranging between 0.5 and 1).

2.5.2. Results

• CALCULATION OF THE EQUIVALENT VISCOUS DAMPING, see equation C7.3.10, Circular 2019

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force max =			1431.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	15.249 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	715.7 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	1.809 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1095.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	4.414 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.139 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.358 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	10.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.795
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.059 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1207.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	6.622 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.153 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.418 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	12.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.748
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.069 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.966

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1416.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	28.274 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.179 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.797 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	21.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.612
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.175 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.875

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1220.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	37.699 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.155 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.991 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	28.6 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.209 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1677.4 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	32.616 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	838.7 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	1.764 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1147.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.547 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.145 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.266 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	6.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.954
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.052 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1424.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	3.820 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.180 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.292 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	8.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.855
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.072 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.999

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1666.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	24.462 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.211 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.683 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	22.2 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.606
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.179 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.891

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1677.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	32.616 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.212 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.786 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	23.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.597
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.210 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^* =	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^* =	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max} =	1460.2 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max} =	15.390 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50} =	730.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50} =	1.854 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1} =	1082.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1} =	4.138 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS} =	0.137 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS} =	0.349 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	10.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.813
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS} =	0.057 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2} =	1230.8 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2} =	6.208 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS} =	0.156 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS} =	0.400 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	11.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.769
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS} =	0.069 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	0.958

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3} =	1443.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3} =	27.427 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS} =	0.183 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS} =	0.777 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	21.6 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.613
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C =	0.174 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	0.868

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4} =	1249.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4} =	36.569 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS} =	0.158 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS} =	0.965 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	28.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS} =	0.208 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1678.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	32.333 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	839.0 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	1.810 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1071.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.503 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.136 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.273 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.997
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.046

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1414.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	3.754 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.179 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.290 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	7.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.899
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.068 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.942

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1668.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	24.250 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.211 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.680 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	22.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.607
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.178 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.885

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1678.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	32.333 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.212 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.783 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	23.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.597
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.209 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^* =	751.6 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^* =	1.327
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max} =	1441.0 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max} =	15.671 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50} =	720.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50} =	1.985 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1} =	1070.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1} =	4.422 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS} =	0.145 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS} =	0.350 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	10.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.815
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS} =	0.061 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2} =	1224.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2} =	6.633 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS} =	0.166 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS} =	0.401 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	12.6 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.754
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS} =	0.075 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	1.042

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3} =	1427.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3} =	29.496 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS} =	0.194 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS} =	0.783 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	21.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.614
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C =	0.185 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	0.925

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4} =	1226.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4} =	39.328 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS} =	0.166 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS} =	0.976 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	28.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS} =	0.222 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^* =	773.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^* =	1.315
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max} =	1677.9 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max} =	33.762 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50} =	839.0 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50} =	1.882 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1} =	1160.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1} =	2.776 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS} =	0.153 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS} =	0.270 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	5.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.967
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS} =	0.054 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2} =	1420.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2} =	4.164 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS} =	0.187 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS} =	0.299 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	8.6 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.858
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS} =	0.074 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	1.033

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3} =	1671.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3} =	25.321 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS} =	0.220 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS} =	0.680 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	21.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.611
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C =	0.184 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	0.918

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4} =	1677.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4} =	33.762 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS} =	0.221 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS} =	0.784 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	22.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.600
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS} =	0.217 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^* =	751.6 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^* =	1.327
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max} =	1443.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max} =	16.424 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50} =	721.7 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50} =	1.981 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1} =	1062.0 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1} =	4.478 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS} =	0.144 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS} =	0.354 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	9.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.819
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS} =	0.060 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2} =	1220.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2} =	6.717 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS} =	0.166 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS} =	0.404 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	12.2 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.761
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS} =	0.074 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	1.029

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3} =	1427.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3} =	29.496 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS} =	0.194 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS} =	0.783 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	21.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.614
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C =	0.185 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	0.924

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4} =	1228.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4} =	39.328 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS} =	0.167 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS} =	0.975 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	28.6 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS} =	0.222 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	773.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.315
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1692.2 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	33.153 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	846.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	1.950 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1131.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.818 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.149 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.276 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.977
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.052 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1425.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	4.227 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.188 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.301 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	7.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.884
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.072 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.005

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1687.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	24.865 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.223 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.671 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	21.6 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.613
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.183 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.911

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1692.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	33.153 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.223 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.773 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	22.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.601
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.216 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	3004.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	21.400 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	1502.0 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	2.590 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	2208.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	5.201 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.147 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.378 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	9.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.832
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.060 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	2553.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	7.802 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.170 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.430 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	11.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.769
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.075 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.044

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	2957.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	39.450 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.196 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.899 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	22.2 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.606
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.219 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.091

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	2571.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	52.600 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.171 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	1.113 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	28.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.260 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	3150.3 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	19.000 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	1575.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	2.224 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1946.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.821 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.129 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.296 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.982
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.045 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	2668.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	4.231 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.177 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.310 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	6.6 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.928
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.065 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.904

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	2826.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	21.300 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.188 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.676 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	24.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.582
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.164 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.816

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	2880.0 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	28.400 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.191 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.773 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	24.2 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.585
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.190 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	3005.3 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	22.200 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	1502.7 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	2.591 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	2208.8 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	5.207 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.147 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.378 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	9.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.833
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.060 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	2553.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	7.811 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.170 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.431 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	11.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.769
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.075 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.043

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	2957.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	39.450 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.196 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.899 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	22.2 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.606
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.219 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.091

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	2591.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	52.600 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.172 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	1.109 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	28.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.261 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^* = 1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^* = 1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max} = 3113.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max} = 18.800 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50} = 1556.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50} = 2.238 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1} = 1846.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1} = 2.789 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS} = 0.123 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS} = 0.303 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} = 5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} = 1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS} = 0.042 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2} = 2614.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2} = 4.183 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS} = 0.174 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS} = 0.311 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} = 5.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} = 0.957
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS} = 0.062 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$ = 0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ = 0.859

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3} = 2832.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3} = 21.225 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS} = 0.188 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS} = 0.674 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} = 24.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} = 0.588
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C = 0.162 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$ = 0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ = 0.808

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4} = 2885.8 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4} = 28.300 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS} = 0.192 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS} = 0.771 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} = 23.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} = 0.589
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS} = 0.188 g

- CALCULATION OF THE EQUIVALENT VISCOUS DAMPING, see eq. 5.6, in Lagomarsino and Cattari [7]

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1431.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	15.249 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	858.9 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	2.422 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	5.4 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	1037.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	3.843 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	854.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.400 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.108 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.299 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.037 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1248.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	7.201 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.158 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.428 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	12.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.767
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.070 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.975

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1416.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	28.274 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.179 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.797 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.660
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.163 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.811

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1220.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	37.699 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.155 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.991 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.653
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.176 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1677.4 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	32.616 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	1006.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	2.172 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	8.7 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	1425.8 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	3.820 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1174.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.683 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.149 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.270 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.051 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1632.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	8.048 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.207 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.396 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	12.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.748
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.094 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.308

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1666.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	24.462 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.211 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.683 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	17.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.664
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.163 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.813

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1677.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	32.616 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.212 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.786 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.2 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.656
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.191 g

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1460.2 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	15.390 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	876.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	2.525 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	5.7 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	1062.2 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	3.917 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	874.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.541 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.111 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.304 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.038 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1312.0 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	7.624 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.166 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.430 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	12.3 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.760
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.074 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	z_{PGA_D}	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	ζ_{E}	=	1.034

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1443.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	27.427 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.183 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.777 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	17.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.661
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.161 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	z_{PGA_D}	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	ζ_{E}	=	0.804

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1249.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	36.569 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.158 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.965 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.654
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.175 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1678.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	32.333 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	1006.8 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	2.232 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	8.8 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	1426.4 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	3.754 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1174.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.824 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.149 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.276 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.051 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1655.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	8.472 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.210 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.403 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	13.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.738
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.097 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.343

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1668.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	24.250 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.211 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.680 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	17.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.664
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.162 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.810

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1678.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	32.333 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.212 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.783 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.3 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.656
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.190 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	751.6 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.327
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1441.0 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	15.671 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	864.6 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	2.696 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	5.2 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	1042.3 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	4.115 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	858.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.712 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.116 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.306 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.040 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1291.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	8.137 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.175 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.432 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	12.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.758
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.079 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.094

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1427.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	29.496 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.194 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.783 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	17.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.661
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.172 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.859

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1226.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	39.328 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.166 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.976 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.653
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.186 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	773.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.315
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1677.9 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	33.762 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	1006.7 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	2.318 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	8.5 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	1426.2 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	4.164 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1174.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.890 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.155 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.274 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.053 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1613.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	8.669 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.213 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.405 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	12.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.750
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.097 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.342

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1671.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	25.321 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.220 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.680 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	17.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.666
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.169 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.842

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1677.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	33.762 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.221 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.784 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.657
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.198 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^* =	751.6 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^* =	1.327
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max} =	1443.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max} =	16.424 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60} =	866.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60} =	2.711 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^* =	5.2 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y =	1044.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y =	4.160 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1} =	859.8 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1} =	2.712 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS} =	0.117 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS} =	0.306 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS} =	0.040 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2} =	1292.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2} =	8.137 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS} =	0.175 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS} =	0.432 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	12.3 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.760
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS} =	0.079 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	z_{PGA_D} =	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	1.092

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3} =	1427.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3} =	29.496 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS} =	0.194 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS} =	0.783 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	17.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.661
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C =	0.172 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	z_{PGA_D} =	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	0.859

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4} =	1228.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4} =	39.328 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS} =	0.167 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS} =	0.975 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	18.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.654
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS} =	0.187 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	773.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.315
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1692.2 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	33.153 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	1015.3 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	2.405 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	8.8 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	1438.4 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	4.227 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1184.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	3.042 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.156 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.280 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.053 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1636.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	9.125 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.216 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.413 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	13.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.744
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.099 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.372

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1687.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	24.865 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.223 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.671 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	17.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.667
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.168 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.837

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1692.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	33.153 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.223 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.773 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.658
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.197 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	3004.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	21.400 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	1802.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	3.460 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	8.1 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	2185.9 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	5.081 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1800.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	3.600 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.120 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.348 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.041 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	2820.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	10.800 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.187 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.482 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	12.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.747
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.091 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.262

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	2957.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	39.450 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.196 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.899 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.658
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.201 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.005

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	2571.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	52.600 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.171 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	1.113 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.6 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.652
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.219 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	3150.3 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	19.000 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	1890.2 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	2.712 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	17.5 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	2448.0 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	3.655 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	2016.0 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	3.000 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.134 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.300 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.046 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	3076.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	9.000 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.204 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.421 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	13.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.727
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.096 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.330

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	2826.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	21.300 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.188 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.676 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	17.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.668
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.143 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.711

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	2880.0 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	28.400 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.191 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.773 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.658
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.169 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	3005.3 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	22.200 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	1803.2 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	3.463 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	8.2 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	2202.8 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	5.169 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1814.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	3.600 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.121 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.347 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.041 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	2820.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	10.800 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.187 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.482 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	12.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.749
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.090 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.258

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	2957.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	39.450 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.196 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.899 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.659
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.201 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.004

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	2591.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	52.600 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.172 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	1.109 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.652
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.220 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	3113.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	18.800 mm
60% of the maximum force value:	F_{60}	=	1867.9 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{60}	=	2.735 mm
Initial stiffness of 1DOF system:	k^*	=	17.6 kN / mm
Elastic force in the equivalent 1DOF system:	F_y	=	2452.9 kN
Displacement corresponding to the elastic force:	d_y	=	3.762 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	2020.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	3.000 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.134 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.300 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	1.000
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.046 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	3039.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	9.000 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.202 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.424 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	13.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.731
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.094 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.307

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	2832.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	21.225 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.188 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.674 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	17.3 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.669
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.142 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.710

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	2885.8 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	28.300 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.192 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.771 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	18.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.659
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.168 g

2.5.3. Seismic vulnerability

The analyses carried out and reported in the previous section have allowed an assessment of the safety level of the building at the limit states LS1, LS2, LS3, LS4, expressed by the risk indexes $\zeta_E(\text{LS}_i)$ in terms of PGA (peak ground acceleration). Those indexes represent the ratio, in terms of acceleration, between the capacity and the demand of the structure, *i.e.* between the seismic forces that the building is able to withstand and those formally required by the National Code,

$$\zeta_E(\text{LS}_i) = \frac{\text{PGA}_C(\text{LS}_i)}{\text{PGA}_D(\text{LS}_i)}$$

where $\text{PGA}_C(\text{LS}_i)$ is the capacity acceleration for the i -th limit state, $i = 1, \dots, 4$; $\text{PGA}_D(\text{LS}_i)$ is the corresponding peak ground acceleration (demand).

In Tables 2.5 and 2.6 are summarized the results of the seismic vulnerability, respectively at the Limit State of Life Safety SLV (LS3) and the Limit State of Damage SLD (LS2). In each table, for all load cases LC01, ..., LC12, the performance points in terms of displacement and corresponding force, the equivalent viscous damping defined in equation C7.3.10, Circular 2019, the capacity acceleration, the risk index, are reported.

In seismic retrofitting of buildings, Circular 2019 generally requires that the unit value of parameter ζ_E be achieved, as for new constructions. On the other hand, in the case of simple changes in class and/or intended use that involve increases in vertical loads on the footings of more than 10%, a minimum value of ζ_E equal to 0.8 is permitted. That situation is also comparable to seismic retrofitting decided after inadequacies were found through the assessment of seismic vulnerability of the existing building in its current configuration, as in the case study examined here.

Therefore, at SLV the resistance capacity of the building is adequate, since $\zeta_E > 0.80$: in the most severe load cases, the risk index is equal to 0.87 and 0.81, respectively in the longitudinal and transversal directions.

For comparison, in Tables 2.7 and 2.8 are summarized the results of the seismic vulnerability, respectively at the Limit State of Life Safety SLV (LS3) and the Limit State of Damage SLD (LS2). In each table, for all load cases LC1, ..., LC12, the performance points in terms of displacement and corresponding force, the equivalent viscous damping defined in (Calvi, 1999), the capacity acceleration, the risk index are reported.

It should be noted that the risk indices are slightly lower, since the evaluation of the equivalent viscous damping yields a lower value than the formula proposed in Circular 2019.

Table 2.5. Calculation of the performance point in the Limit State of Life Safety, equivalent viscous damping using equation C7.3.10 of Circular 2019, risk index, for all load cases. Acceleration demand at limit state LS3 for new buildings: 0.201 g.

LCCase	D_LS3 [mm]	F_LS3 [kN]	Xi_eq [%]	PGA_C [g]	zeta_E [%]
LC01	40.1	2006.2	21.7	0.175	0.875
LC02	34.7	2361.1	22.2	0.179	0.891
LC03	38.9	2044.8	21.6	0.174	0.868
LC04	34.4	2363.7	22.1	0.178	0.885
LC05	39.1	1895.0	21.5	0.185	0.925
LC06	33.3	2198.0	21.8	0.184	0.918
LC07	39.1	1894.4	21.5	0.185	0.924
LC08	32.7	2219.0	21.6	0.183	0.911
LC09	39.5	2957.5	22.2	0.219	1.091
LC10	21.3	2826.2	24.5	0.164	0.816
LC11	39.5	2957.5	22.2	0.219	1.091
LC12	21.2	2832.6	24.0	0.162	0.808

Table 2.6. Calculation of the performance point in the Limit State of Damage, equivalent viscous damping using equation C7.3.10 of Circular 2019, risk index, for all load cases. Acceleration demand at limit state LS2 for new buildings: 0.072 g.

LCCase	D_LS2 [mm]	F_LS2 [kN]	Xi_eq [%]	PGA_C [g]	zeta_E [%]
LC01	9.4	1710.3	12.9	0.069	0.966
LC02	5.4	2018.4	8.7	0.072	0.999
LC03	8.8	1743.4	11.9	0.069	0.958
LC04	5.3	2003.5	7.4	0.068	0.942
LC05	8.8	1625.4	12.6	0.075	1.042
LC06	5.5	1867.7	8.6	0.074	1.033
LC07	8.9	1620.2	12.2	0.074	1.029
LC08	5.6	1874.7	7.8	0.072	1.005
LC09	7.8	2553.2	11.9	0.075	1.044
LC10	4.2	2668.7	6.6	0.065	0.904
LC11	7.8	2553.2	11.9	0.075	1.043
LC12	4.2	2614.5	5.9	0.062	0.859

Table 2.7. Calculation of the performance point in the Limit State of Life Safety, equivalent viscous damping using the equation proposed in (Calvi, 1999), risk index, for all load cases. Acceleration demand at limit state LS3 for new buildings: 0.201 g.

LCCase	D_LS3	F_LS3	Xi_eq	PGA_C	zeta_E
	[mm]	[kN]	[%]	[g]	[%]
LC01	40.1	2006.2	18.0	0.163	0.811
LC02	34.7	2361.1	17.7	0.163	0.813
LC03	38.9	2044.8	17.9	0.161	0.804
LC04	34.4	2363.7	17.7	0.162	0.810
LC05	39.1	1895.0	17.9	0.172	0.859
LC06	33.3	2198.0	17.5	0.169	0.842
LC07	39.1	1894.4	17.9	0.172	0.859
LC08	32.7	2219.0	17.5	0.168	0.837
LC09	39.5	2957.5	18.1	0.201	1.005
LC10	21.3	2826.2	17.4	0.143	0.711
LC11	39.5	2957.5	18.0	0.201	1.004
LC12	21.2	2832.6	17.3	0.142	0.710

Table 2.8. Calculation of the performance point in the Limit State of Damage, equivalent viscous damping using the equation proposed in (Calvi, 1999), risk index, for all load cases. Acceleration demand at limit state LS2 for new buildings: 0.072 g.

LCCase	D_LS2	F_LS2	Xi_eq	PGA_C	zeta_E
	[mm]	[kN]	[%]	[g]	[%]
LC01	10.2	1768.4	12.0	0.070	0.975
LC02	11.4	2312.5	12.9	0.094	1.308
LC03	10.8	1858.4	12.3	0.074	1.034
LC04	12.0	2344.9	13.4	0.097	1.343
LC05	10.8	1714.5	12.4	0.079	1.094
LC06	11.4	2121.5	12.8	0.097	1.342
LC07	10.8	1715.6	12.3	0.079	1.092
LC08	12.0	2152.3	13.1	0.099	1.372
LC09	10.8	2820.7	12.9	0.091	1.262
LC10	9.0	3076.5	13.9	0.096	1.330
LC11	10.8	2820.6	12.8	0.090	1.258
LC12	9.0	3039.4	13.7	0.094	1.307

Finally, the following Figures 2.10-2.17 show the hinge status for the shear and flexural components in piers and spandrels at the ultimate load-carrying capacity (collapse limit). The two most severe load cases in the longitudinal and transverse directions are considered.

Fig. 2.10 Hinge status for the shear component in piers at the ultimate load-carrying capacity (collapse limit). Load case LC03; Seismic forces in the longitudinal direction.

Fig. 2.11 Hinge status for the bending component in piers at the ultimate load-carrying capacity (collapse limit). Load case LC03; Seismic forces in the longitudinal direction.

Fig. 2.12 Hinge status for the shear component in spandrels at the ultimate load-carrying capacity (collapse limit). Load case LC03; Seismic forces in the longitudinal direction.

Fig. 2.13 Hinge status for the bending component in spandrels at the ultimate load-carrying capacity (collapse limit). Load case LC03; Seismic forces in the longitudinal direction.

Fig. 2.14 Hinge status for the shear component in piers at the ultimate load-carrying capacity (collapse limit). Load case LC12; Seismic forces in the transversal direction.

Fig. 2.15 Hinge status for the bending component in piers at the ultimate load-carrying capacity (collapse limit). Load case LC12; Seismic forces in the transversal direction.

Fig. 2.16 Hinge status for the shear component in spandrels at the ultimate load-carrying capacity (collapse limit). Load case LC12; Seismic forces in the transversal direction.

Fig. 2.17 Hinge status for the bending component in spandrels at the ultimate load-carrying capacity (collapse limit). Load case LC12; Seismic forces in the transversal direction.

2.5.4. Additional insights

In Section 2.4.2, the bending and shear in-plane capacity of strengthening wall panels, were calculated using the expressions proposed in CNR-DT 215/2018. In particular, in the calculation of the strengthening, the contribution $V_{t,f}$ took into account the coefficient $\alpha_T = 0.80$, due to the reduced tensile strength of the fibres when subjected to shear stress and the 30% reduction in the presence of reinforcement on only one side of the wall. The contribution $V_{t,f}$ was reduced by a factor of $0.8 \cdot 0.7 = 0.56$, while the other partial safety coefficients of the material remain unchanged.

However, it should be noted that, on the one hand, the CNR-DT215 guidelines refer to FRCM materials for structural strengthening; on the other hand, from the extensive testing campaign and numerical analyses on CRM-reinforced wall panels, it emerged that shear capacity is not influenced by the two reducing factors considered above. Consequently, the yield strengths of the plastic hinges in the piers and spandrels were increased in an updated FE model (RM-UPD configuration), pushover analyses were carried out, new capacity curves were calculated for all load cases summarised in Table 2.1. The performance points for limit states LS1, LS2, LS3, LS4 were determined on the force-displacement curves using the CSM method in accordance with Circular 2019.

In Tables 2.9 and 2.10 the results of the seismic vulnerability are summarised at the Limit State of Life Safety SLV (LS3) and the Limit State of Damage SLD (LS2), respectively. For all load cases LC01, ..., LC12, the performance points in terms of displacement and corresponding force, the equivalent viscous damping defined in equation C7.3.10, Circular 2019, the capacity acceleration, the risk index, are reported.

In seismic retrofitting of buildings, Circular 2019 generally requires that the unit value of parameter ζ_E be achieved, as for new constructions. On the other hand, in the case of simple changes in class and/or intended use that involve increases in vertical loads on the footings of more than 10%, a minimum value of ζ_E equal to 0.8 is permitted. That situation is also comparable to seismic retrofitting decided after inadequacies were found through the safety assessment of the existing building in its current configuration, as in the case study examined.

Therefore, at SLV the resistance capacity of the building is adequate, since $\zeta_E > 0.80$: in the most severe load cases, the risk index is equal to 0.93 and 0.83, respectively in the longitudinal and transversal directions. As expected, in the updated model the risk indices are slightly higher, about 0.06 and 0.03.

Table 2.9. Calculation of the performance point with update values in the plastic hinges at the Limit State of Life Safety, equivalent viscous damping using equation C7.3.10 of Circular 2019, risk index, for all load cases. Acceleration demand at limit state LS3 for new buildings: 0.201 g.

LCCase	D_LS3	F_LS3	Xi_eq	PGA_C	zeta_E
	[mm]	[kN]	[%]	[g]	[%]
LC01	39.9	2314.1	21.9	0.189	0.940
LC02	34.4	2558.1	21.6	0.183	0.912
LC03	39.9	2313.8	21.8	0.188	0.939
LC04	33.2	2560.5	21.5	0.179	0.895
LC05	40.0	2141.3	21.9	0.201	1.002
LC06	33.0	2379.3	21.5	0.190	0.946
LC07	39.9	2144.8	21.8	0.200	0.999
LC08	32.6	2394.7	21.2	0.188	0.937
LC09	39.2	3366.9	22.0	0.232	1.156
LC10	21.5	3035.7	23.9	0.168	0.840
LC11	39.2	3376.1	22.0	0.232	1.156
LC12	21.5	3043.5	23.4	0.167	0.834

Table 2.10. Calculation of the performance point with update values in the plastic hinges at the Limit State of Damage, equivalent viscous damping using equation C7.3.10 of Circular 2019, risk index, for all load cases. Acceleration demand at limit state LS2 for new buildings: 0.072 g.

LCCase	D_LS2	F_LS2	Xi_eq	PGA_C	zeta_E
	[mm]	[kN]	[%]	[g]	[%]
LC01	8.0	1988.2	11.3	0.077	1.075
LC02	5.9	2167.0	8.2	0.076	1.052
LC03	8.1	1980.5	11.0	0.076	1.061
LC04	5.8	2177.5	7.9	0.075	1.048
LC05	8.1	1832.0	10.9	0.080	1.119
LC06	6.0	2026.1	8.9	0.082	1.134
LC07	8.2	1832.1	10.8	0.080	1.114
LC08	6.0	2035.4	8.4	0.080	1.118
LC09	7.0	2866.3	9.1	0.077	1.070
LC10	4.6	2838.3	6.4	0.069	0.955
LC11	7.0	2866.3	9.0	0.077	1.066
LC12	4.5	2817.1	6.4	0.068	0.945

Below are the extended printouts with the evaluation of the performance points for limit states LS1, LS2, LS3, LS4, (CSM method as in Circular 2019), the equivalent viscous coefficient, the acceleration capacity, the demand in terms of acceleration.

• CALCULATION OF THE EQUIVALENT VISCOUS DAMPING, see equation C7.3.10, Circular 2019

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1652.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	14.967 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	826.0 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	2.051 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1209.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	3.771 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.153 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.315 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	7.6 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.892
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.058 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1403.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	5.656 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.178 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.358 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	11.3 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.782
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.077 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.075

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1633.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	28.168 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.207 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.740 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	21.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.610
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.189 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.940

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1424.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	37.558 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.180 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.916 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	28.3 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.225 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1808.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	32.333 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	904.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	1.919 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1196.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	2.773 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.152 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.271 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.977
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.053 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1529.8 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	4.159 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.194 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.294 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	8.2 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.871
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.076 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.052

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1805.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	24.250 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.229 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.653 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	21.6 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.613
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.183 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.912

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1808.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	32.333 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.229 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.754 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	22.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.600
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.216 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^* =	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^* =	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max} =	1651.6 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max} =	15.249 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50} =	825.8 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50} =	2.045 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1} =	1201.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1} =	3.812 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS} =	0.152 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS} =	0.318 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	7.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.897
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS} =	0.058 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2} =	1398.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2} =	5.718 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS} =	0.177 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS} =	0.361 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	11.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.790
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS} =	0.076 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	1.061

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3} =	1633.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3} =	28.168 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS} =	0.207 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS} =	0.740 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	21.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.610
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C =	0.188 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	0.939

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4} =	1418.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4} =	37.558 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS} =	0.180 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS} =	0.918 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	28.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS} =	0.225 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^* =	805.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^* =	1.416
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max} =	1812.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max} =	31.204 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50} =	906.2 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50} =	1.976 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1} =	1172.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1} =	2.746 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS} =	0.148 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS} =	0.273 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	5.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.968
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS} =	0.052 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2} =	1537.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2} =	4.118 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS} =	0.195 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS} =	0.292 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	7.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.879
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS} =	0.075 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	1.048

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3} =	1807.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3} =	23.403 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS} =	0.229 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS} =	0.642 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	21.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.615
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C =	0.179 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	0.895

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4} =	1812.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4} =	31.204 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS} =	0.230 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS} =	0.740 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	22.7 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.601
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS} =	0.212 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	751.6 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.327
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1632.4 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	15.972 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	816.2 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	2.196 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1207.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	4.083 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.164 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.317 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	8.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.863
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.065 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1380.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	6.125 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.187 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.363 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	10.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.792
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.080 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.119

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1613.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	30.174 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.219 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.745 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	21.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.609
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.201 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.002

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1389.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	40.232 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.189 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.927 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	28.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.239 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^* =	773.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^* =	1.315
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max} =	1815.9 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max} =	33.457 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50} =	908.0 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50} =	2.058 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1} =	1254.8 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1} =	3.061 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS} =	0.165 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS} =	0.273 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	6.2 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.944
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS} =	0.060 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2} =	1540.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2} =	4.591 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS} =	0.203 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS} =	0.302 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	8.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.847
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS} =	0.082 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	1.134

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3} =	1809.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3} =	25.093 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS} =	0.239 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS} =	0.651 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	21.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.614
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C =	0.190 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$ =	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ =	0.946

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4} =	1815.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4} =	33.457 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS} =	0.239 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS} =	0.750 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} =	22.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} =	0.603
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS} =	0.224 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	751.6 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.327
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1634.0 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	16.123 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	817.0 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	2.184 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1204.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	4.102 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.163 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.318 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	8.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.863
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.064 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1380.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	6.153 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.187 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.364 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	10.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.795
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.080 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.114

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1615.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	30.061 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.219 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.743 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	21.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.611
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.200 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.999

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1389.4 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	40.081 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.189 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.925 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	28.8 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.238 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	773.3 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.315
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	1825.8 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	33.001 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	912.9 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	2.127 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	1230.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	3.065 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.162 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.276 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	6.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.948
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.058 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	1547.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	4.598 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.204 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.301 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	8.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.863
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.080 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	z_{PGA_D}	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.118

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	1820.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	24.751 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.240 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.644 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	21.2 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.618
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.188 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	z_{PGA_D}	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.937

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	1825.8 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	33.001 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.241 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.743 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	22.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.604
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.222 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^* = 1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^* = 1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max} = 3403.8 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max} = 20.600 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50} = 1701.9 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50} = 2.854 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1} = 2391.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1} = 4.640 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS} = 0.159 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS} = 0.343 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} = 7.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} = 0.912
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS} = 0.059 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2} = 2866.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2} = 6.960 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS} = 0.190 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS} = 0.384 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} = 9.1 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} = 0.842
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS} = 0.077 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$ = 0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ = 1.070

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3} = 3366.9 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3} = 39.150 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS} = 0.224 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS} = 0.839 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} = 22.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} = 0.608
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C = 0.232 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$ = 0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$ = 1.156

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4} = 2906.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4} = 52.200 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS} = 0.193 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS} = 1.043 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq} = 29.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq} = 0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS} = 0.275 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	3361.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	19.200 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	1680.6 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	2.384 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	2067.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	3.043 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.137 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.299 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.3 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.984
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.047 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	2838.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	4.565 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.189 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.312 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	6.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.935
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.069 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.955

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	3035.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	21.450 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.202 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.654 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	23.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.588
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.168 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.840

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	3089.7 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	28.600 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.205 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.749 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	23.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.588
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.196 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	3409.8 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	22.800 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	1704.9 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	2.860 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	2391.2 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	4.660 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.159 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.344 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	6.9 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.915
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.059 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	2866.3 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	6.990 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.190 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.384 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	9.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.845
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.077 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	z_{PGA_D}	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.066

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	3376.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	39.150 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.224 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.838 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	22.0 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.609
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.232 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	z_{PGA_D}	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	1.156

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	2953.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	52.200 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.196 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	1.035 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	28.3 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.550
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.277 g

Capacity Spectrum vs. Demand Spectrum

EQUIVALENT 1DOF SYSTEM

Mass of the 1DOF system	m^*	=	1534.9 kN s**2 / m
Evaluation of modal participation factor:	G^*	=	1.000
Maximum value of equivalent 1DOF system force:	F_{max}	=	3325.1 kN
Displacement corresponding to the maximum force:	D_{max}	=	19.100 mm
50% of the maximum force value:	F_{50}	=	1662.5 kN
Displacement corresponding to 60% of the maximum force:	F_{50}	=	2.404 mm

LIMIT STATE LS1

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS1:	F_{LS1}	=	2026.6 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	D_{LS1}	=	3.018 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	a_{LS}	=	0.135 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS1:	T_{LS}	=	0.300 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	5.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.974
Ground acceleration at limit state LS1:	ag_{LS}	=	0.047 g

LIMIT STATE LS2

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS2:	F_{LS2}	=	2817.1 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	D_{LS2}	=	4.528 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	a_{LS}	=	0.187 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS2:	T_{LS}	=	0.312 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	6.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.937
Ground acceleration at limit state LS2:	ag_{LS}	=	0.068 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS2:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.072 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.945

LIMIT STATE LS3

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS3:	F_{LS3}	=	3043.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	D_{LS3}	=	21.450 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	a_{LS}	=	0.202 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS3:	T_{LS}	=	0.654 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	23.4 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.593
Ground acceleration at limit state LS3:	PGA_C	=	0.167 g
Acceleration demand at limit state LS3:	$zPGA_D$	=	0.201 g
Capacity to demand ratio:	$zeta_E$	=	0.834

LIMIT STATE LS4

Force in the equivalent 1DOF system at limit state LS4:	F_{LS4}	=	3097.5 kN
Displacement in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	D_{LS4}	=	28.600 mm
Acceleration in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	a_{LS}	=	0.206 g
Period in the equivalent 1DOF at limit state LS4:	T_{LS}	=	0.748 s
Calculation of the equivalent viscous damping:	ξ_{eq}	=	23.5 %
Reduced demand capacity spectrum:	η_{eq}	=	0.592
Ground acceleration at limit state LS4:	ag_{LS}	=	0.195 g

2.6. Comparison of the pushover analyses (URM and RM configurations)

Fig. 2.18 plots the capacity curves for the building in: (i) the unreinforced configuration (URM); (ii) the reinforced configuration (RM), where the bending and shear in-plane capacity of strengthening wall panels were calculated using the expressions proposed in CNR-DT 215/2018; (iii) the updated reinforced configuration (RM-UPD), in which the reduced factor $0.8 \cdot 0.7 = 0.56$ was neglected in the contribution $V_{t,f}$ of the shear capacity.

The load case LC03 has been considered for all three configurations, corresponding to a distribution of seismic forces, in the longitudinal direction, proportional to the lateral method in the static analysis. Strengthening with CRM materials significantly increases the maximum shear resultant force at the base of the building (56% or 76% in RM or RM-UPD configurations) and has a favourable effect on the ultimate displacement when the performance point at limit state LS4 is reached.

Fig. 2.19 and Table 2.12 show a similar comparison in load case LC04, corresponding to a distribution of seismic forces proportional to the lateral method in the static analysis in the transversal direction. Here, the response of the building is completely different. In the unstrengthened configuration URM, the overall behaviour is brittle (cracking due to shear of the masonry units). In the reinforced configurations (RM, RM-UPD), there is a significant increase in ductility, with displacements at limit state LS4 approximately 2.4 times those of the URM case, while the increase in maximum reaction is around 12 and 21% for the RM and RM-UPD cases, respectively.

Fig. 2.18. Capacity curves for the building in the unreinforced configuration (URM) and reinforced configurations (RM, RM-UPD). Seismic force in longitudinal direction, load case LC03.

Fig. 2.19. Capacity curves for the building in the unreinforced configuration (URM) and reinforced configurations (RM, RM-UPD). Seismic force in transversal direction, load case LC04.

Table 2.11. Maximum intensity of the force and ultimate displacement at limit state LS4 in the capacity curves (RM, RM-UPD) of Fig. 2.18. Seismic force in longitudinal direction, load case LC03. $\Delta 1 = 100 \cdot (X(\text{RM}) - X(\text{URM})) / X(\text{URM})$; $\Delta 2 = 100 \cdot (X(\text{RM-UPD}) - X(\text{URM})) / X(\text{URM})$.

X	URM	RM	$\Delta 1$ (%)	RM-UPD	$\Delta 2$ (%)
F_{\max} [kN]	1327.9	2067.6	56 %	2338.7	76 %
D(LS4) [mm]	45.8	51.8	13 %	53.2	16 %

Table 2.12. Maximum intensity of the force and ultimate displacement at limit state LS4 in the capacity curves (RM, RM-UPD) of Fig. 2.19. Seismic force in transversal direction, load case LC04. $\Delta 1 = 100 \cdot (X(\text{RM}) - X(\text{URM})) / X(\text{URM})$; $\Delta 2 = 100 \cdot (X(\text{RM-UPD}) - X(\text{URM})) / X(\text{URM})$.

X	URM	RM	$\Delta 1$ (%)	RM-UPD	$\Delta 2$ (%)
F_{\max} [kN]	2124.0	2376.2	12 %	2566.5	21 %
D(LS4) [mm]	18.7	45.8	145 %	44.2	136 %

Finally, Tables 2.13, 2.14, show the risk indices, respectively at LS2 and LS3, in the most unfavourable load cases. The increase in seismic safety following the building retrofitting is quite evident.

Table 2.13. Seismic vulnerability in longitudinal and transversal directions at the Limit State of Damage LS2 for the building in the unreinforced configuration (URM) and reinforced configurations (RM, RM-UPD).

$a_{g,\max}$ LS2	Longitudinal direction (X)				Transversal direction (Y)		
	Building config.	$a_{g,d}$	Load case	$a_{g,c}$	ζE	Load case	$a_{g,c}$
URM	0.072 g	LC01	0.060 g	0.83	LC12	0.054 g	0.75
RM	0.072 g	LC03	0.069 g	0.96	LC12	0.062 g	0.86
RM-UPD	0.072 g	LC03	0.076 g	1.06	LC12	0.068 g	0.95

Table 2.14. Seismic vulnerability in longitudinal and transversal directions at the Limit State of Life Safety LS3 for the building in the unreinforced configuration (URM) and reinforced configurations (RM, RM-UPD).

a_{g,max} LS3	a_{g,d}	Longitudinal direction (X)			Transversal direction (Y)		
		Load case	a_{g,c}	ζE	Load case	a_{g,c}	ζE
URM	0.201 g	LC03	0.121 g	0.60	LC04	0.092 g	0.46
RM	0.201 g	LC03	0.174 g	0.87	LC12	0.162 g	0.81
RM-UPD	0.201 g	LC03	0.185 g	0.92	LC12	0.167g	0.83

2.7. Structural drawing of the intervention

The structural drawings of the strengthening intervention are included in ANNEX A of this Report.

2.8. Cost estimation for the reinforcement intervention

The bill of quantities of the strengthening intervention is included in ANNEX B of this Report.

3. The building of ZVKDS in Ljubljana strengthened with CRM

3.1. General information

3.1.1. *Description of the structure*

The analysis of building's earthquake resistance before the intervention, documented in PRO-SIS Report 3.3 [1], showed low values, so strengthening measures had to be taken.

By contemporary Slovenian building law, all buildings and also reconstructions must fulfil requirements from the Eurocodes (for masonry, Eurocode 6 and 8 - SIST EN 1996-1-1:2006 and SIST EN 1998-1:2005, both with national appendix).

To that, all perimeter walls of the building were reinforced with the CRM system only on the inside, because the facades are under cultural heritage protection, as evidenced in PRO-SIS Report 3.1 [5]. It was also necessary to reinforce a significant number of internal walls, in order to achieve the required seismic resistance of the building. The masonry walls around stone stairs are also strengthened with CRM, due to fragile system of stairs (cantilever consoles built into the wall).

The reinforcement layout is shown in Fig. 3.1-Fig. 3.4. According to the colour legend below, red represents the basic unreinforced wall (URM), and green represents the reinforcement of the walls with the CRM system. Light green marks the walls where reinforcement is planned on both sides, otherwise the reinforcement is one-sided.

Name	Type	Colour	Description
C14 Conifers, poplar	Wood		EN 338:2002
old_brick_Ljubljana	Masonry		old solid brick masonry in Ljubljana
FRCM_60	Masonry		old solid brick masonry in Ljubljana thickenss 60
FRCM_45	Masonry		old solid brick masonry in Ljubljana thickenss 45
FRCM_75	Masonry		old solid brick masonry in Ljubljana thickenss 75
FRCM_30-1	Masonry		old solid brick masonry in Ljubljana thickenss 30
FRCM_15-2	Masonry		old solid brick masonry in Ljubljana thickenss 15

Fig. 3.1 building model – ground floor.

Fig. 3.2 building model – first floor.

Fig. 3.3 building model – second floor.

Fig. 3.4 building model – attic.

3.1.2. Reference Standard Codes

Eurocode 6 and 8 (SIST EN 1996-1-1:2006 and SIST EN 1998-1:2005 both with national appendix) were applied. Besides, also Italian Circular no. 7/C.S.LL.PP, January 21, 2019 (Instructions for the application of the Update of the “Technical Standards for Construction” referred to in Ministerial Decree 19 January 2018) was considered. In addition, for the design of the reinforcement, the guidelines CNR-DT 215/2018 “Fuide for the design and construction of externally bonded fibre reinforced inorganic matrix systems for strenghtening existing structures” were applied.

3.2. Parameters of materials

The elastic and shear modulus (E , G) of strengthened wall (composite behaviour) are calculated with equations:

$$E_{frcm} = \frac{E_m \cdot t_m + n_{fc} \cdot E_{fc} \cdot t_{fc}}{t_m}$$

$$G_{frcm} = \frac{G_m \cdot t_m + n_{fc} \cdot G_{fc} \cdot t_{fc}}{t_m}$$

with pedix m and fc referring to unstrengthened masonry and mortar of the coating, respectively, and being t the respective thickness and n the number of strengthened sides of the wall.

Results of this for the walls of the building are:

E.m	800	MPa						
G.m	260	MPa						
E.fc	10.000	MPa						
G.fc	4.000	MPa						
t.fc	0,03	m						
t.m [m]	0,75	0,6	0,45	0,3	0,3	0,15	0,15	
sides	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	
E.frcm [MPa]	1200	1300	1467	1800	2800	2800	4800	
G.frcm [MPa]	420	460	527	660	1060	1060	1860	

Masonry

Name	E [N/mm ²]	G [N/mm ²]	Specific weight [kN/m ³]	fm [N/mm ²]	Shear resistance [N/mm ²]
old_brick_Ljubljana	800,00	260,00	16	2,08	0,08
FRCM_60	1.300,00	460,00	16	2,08	0,08
FRCM_30-2	2.800,00	850,00	16	2,08	0,08
FRCM_45	1.466,00	527,00	16	2,08	0,08
FRCM_75	1.200,00	420,00	16	2,08	0,08
FRCM_30-1	1.800,00	660,00	16	2,08	0,08
FRCM_15-2	4.800,00	1.650,00	18	1,67	0,08
FRCM_45i	1.470,00	530,00	16	2,08	0,08

The provided material data from CRM system (t_f , E_f , ε_{fd} , f_{fd}) adopted values in the analysis were (with partial safety factor included):

CRM reinforcement for masonry

Name	Effect typology	Application	Bending anchor	Layers	t_f [mm]	Step [cm]	Area/m [mm ² /m]	η_a	E_f [N/mm ²]	ϵ_{fd} [%]	f_{dd} [N/mm ²]
PRO-SIS_1	Shear+Bending	Single side	Efficacious	1	0,058	0	5,75	0	77.553	1,3636	1.058
PRO-SIS_2	Shear+Bending	Double side	Efficacious	1	0,058	0	5,75	0	77.553	1,3636	1.058
PRO-SIS_2d	Shear+Bending	Double side	Efficacious	1	0,116	0	11,5	0	77.553	1,3636	1.058

	CRM for piers	CRM for spandrels
Shear drift	0.080	0.080
Bending drift	0.016	0.020

3.3. Actions on the structure

The same loading conditions of the unreinforced building described in PRO-SIS Report 3.3 [1] were considered.

3.4. Updated numerical model of the building

Coherently with the approach adopted for the unstrengthened structure [1], the seismic performances of the strengthened building was calculated with the program 3MURI (version 12.6.2.4) - Fig. 3.5.

In accordance to PRO-SIS Report 1.4 [3], and coherently with the CNR-DT 215/2018 approach, the characteristics of reinforced walls were automatically calculated with equations embedded in the program 3MURI, on the basis of the with material data provided for the CRM system (t_f , E_f , ϵ_{fd} , f_{dd}) – as indicated in §3.2.

Fig. 3.5 Analysis 3D model (3MURI); façade on street side (cultural heritage protection); right: back façade.

3.4.1. Numerical model data

- Ground floor**

Masonry panel

No.	Wall	Material	Reinforcement	Elevation [cm]	Height [cm]	Thickness [cm]
1	1	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	75.0
236	2	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	45.0
238	2	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	45.0
239	2	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	45.0
5	3	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	560	560	30.0
45	4	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	560	560	30.0
9	5	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	60.0
232	6	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	45.0
234	6	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	45.0
235	6	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	45.0
13	7	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	560	560	30.0
218	9	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	60.0
222	9	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	60.0
227	9	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	60.0
231	9	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	60.0
257	9	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	60.0
262	9	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	60.0
263	9	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	60.0
217	10	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	560	560	30.0
372	10	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	560	560	30.0
221	11	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	560	560	30.0
371	11	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	560	560	30.0
23	12	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	560	560	30.0
25	13	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_2	560	560	45.0
260	14	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	560	560	45.0
261	14	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	45.0
258	15	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	45.0
259	15	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	45.0
228	16	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	560	560	30.0
229	16	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	560	560	30.0
225	17	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	560	560	30.0
370	17	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	560	560	30.0
183	18	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	560	560	30.0
37	19	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	560	560	45.0
39	20	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	560	560	30.0

Floor

No.	Elevation [cm]	Thickness [cm]	G [N/mm ²]	Ex [N/mm ²]	Ey [N/mm ²]	Mass loading	Type
1	560	4,0	42.066,67	5.250,00	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
2	560	4,0	42.066,67	5.250,00	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
3	560	4,0	42.066,67	2.863,64	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
4	560	4,0	42.066,67	2.863,64	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
5	560	4,0	31.650,00	7.875,00	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
6	560	-	-	-	-	Unidirectional	Rigid floor
7	560	-	-	-	-	Unidirectional	Rigid floor

Vault

No.	Elevation [cm]	Thickness [cm]	G [N/mm ²]	Ex [N/mm ²]	Ey [N/mm ²]	Typology	Total key thickness [cm]	Rise [cm]	Filling density [kN/m ³]	Material
1	560	14,0	202,01	1.212,09	1.212,09	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
2	560	14,0	196,47	1.178,81	1.178,81	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
3	560	14,0	196,91	1.181,43	1.181,43	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
4	560	14,0	195,66	1.173,98	1.173,98	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
5	560	14,0	205,17	1.231,05	1.231,05	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
6	560	14,0	196,61	1.179,65	1.179,65	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
7	560	14,0	195,42	1.172,54	1.172,54	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
8	560	14,0	192,27	1.153,59	1.153,59	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
9	560	14,0	202,15	1.212,91	1.212,91	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
10	560	14,0	201,00	1.205,98	1.205,98	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
11	560	14,0	194,89	1.169,33	1.169,33	Barrel vault	40	40	16	old_brick
12	560	14,0	278,71	1.672,28	1.672,28	Barrel vault	30	20	16	old_brick

• **1st_floor**

Masonry panel

No.	Wall	Material	Reinforcement	Elevation [cm]	Height [cm]	Thickness [cm]
46	1	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	60.0
212	2	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	45.0
214	2	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	45.0
215	2	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	45.0
48	3	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	30.0
49	4	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	30.0
50	5	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	60.0
208	6	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	45.0
210	6	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	45.0
211	6	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	45.0
52	7	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	30.0
190	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	60.0
191	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	60.0
206	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	60.0
207	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	60.0
241	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	60.0

PRO-SIS

252	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	60.0
253	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	60.0
374	10	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	980	420	15.0
375	10	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	980	420	15.0
357	11	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	980	420	15.0
358	12	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	980	420	15.0
57	13	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_2	980	420	45.0
254	14	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	45.0
255	14	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	45.0
109	15	FRCM_30-1	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	30.0
242	15	FRCM_30-1	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	30.0
243	15	FRCM_30-1	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	30.0
366	16	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	980	420	15.0
367	16	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	980	420	15.0
63	19	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	980	420	45.0
64	20	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	980	420	30.0

Floor

No.	Elevation [cm]	Thickness [cm]	G [N/mm ²]	Ex [N/mm ²]	Ey [N/mm ²]	Mass loading	Type
8	980	-	-	-	-	Unidirectional	Rigid floor
9	980	-	-	-	-	Unidirectional	Rigid floor
10	980	4,0	31.650,00	4.295,45	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
11	980	4,0	31.650,00	4.295,45	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
12	980	4,0	31.650,00	4.295,45	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
14	980	4,0	31.650,00	5.250,00	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
15	980	4,0	31.650,00	5.250,00	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault

Vault

No.	Elevation [cm]	Thickness [cm]	G [N/mm ²]	Ex [N/mm ²]	Ey [N/mm ²]	Typology	Total key thickness [cm]	Rise [cm]	Filling density [kN/m ³]	Material
13	980	14,0	258,62	1.551,72	1.551,72	Barrel vault	30	30	16	old_brick
14	980	14,0	149,89	899,33	899,33	Barrel vault	30	30	16	old_brick

Balconies

No.	Wall	Distance from lower level [cm]	Length [cm]	Width [cm]
1	1	25	360	100
2	5	25	883	140
3	5	25	869	140

- **2nd_floor**

Masonry panel

No.	Wall	Material	Reinforcement	Elevation [cm]	Height [cm]	Thickness [cm]
113	1	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	1380	400	60.0
248	2	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	1380	400	45.0
250	2	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	1380	400	45.0
251	2	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	1380	400	45.0
115	3	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	30.0
116	4	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	30.0
117	5	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	1380	400	60.0
244	6	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	1380	400	45.0
246	6	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	1380	400	45.0
247	6	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	1380	400	45.0
119	7	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	30.0
194	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	60.0
195	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	60.0
202	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	60.0
203	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	60.0
266	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	60.0
270	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	60.0
271	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	60.0
192	10	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	15.0
193	10	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	15.0
124	11	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	15.0
126	12	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	15.0
127	13	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	1380	400	45.0
264	14	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	45.0
265	14	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	45.0
129	15	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	30.0
268	15	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	30.0
269	15	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	30.0
196	16	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	15.0
197	16	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	15.0
200	17	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	15.0
201	17	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	15.0
136	19	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	1380	400	45.0
139	20	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	1380	400	30.0

Floor

No.	Elevation [cm]	Thickness [cm]	G [N/mm ²]	Ex [N/mm ²]	Ey [N/mm ²]	Mass loading	Type
16	1.380	-	-	-	-	Unidirectional	Rigid floor
17	1.380	-	-	-	-	Unidirectional	Rigid floor
18	1.380	4,0	31.650,00	4.295,45	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault

19	1.380	4,0	31.650,00	4.295,45	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
20	1.380	4,0	31.650,00	4.295,45	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
21	1.380	4,0	31.650,00	5.250,00	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault
22	1.380	4,0	31.650,00	5.250,00	0,00	Unidirectional	Steel-beam and vault

Vault

No.	Elevation [cm]	Thickness [cm]	G [N/mm ²]	Ex [N/mm ²]	Ey [N/mm ²]	Typology	Total key thickness [cm]	Rise [cm]	Filling density [kN/m ³]	Material
15	1.400	14,0	258,62	1.551,72	1.551,72	Barrel vault	30	30	16	old_brick
16	1.400	14,0	149,89	899,33	899,33	Barrel vault	30	30	16	old_brick

Balconies

No.	Wall	Distance from lower level [cm]	Length [cm]	Width [cm]
5	5	25	883	140
6	5	25	869	140

- **Attic**

Masonry panel

No.	Wall	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]
113	1	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0
142	1	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0
143	2	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0
248	2	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0
250	2	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	45.0
251	2	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0
115	3	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
116	4	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
145	4	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
117	5	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0
146	5	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0
147	6	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0
244	6	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0
246	6	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	45.0
247	6	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0
119	7	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
194	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0
195	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0
202	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0
203	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0
266	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0
270	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0
271	9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0

192	10	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0
193	10	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0
124	11	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0
151	11	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
126	12	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0
127	13	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0
154	14	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
264	14	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0
265	14	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0
129	15	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
155	15	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
268	15	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
269	15	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
156	16	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
196	16	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0
197	16	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0
200	17	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0
201	17	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0
136	19	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0
139	20	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0
160	20	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0

Steel/wooden beam

No.	Wall	Material	Area [cm ²]	J [cm ⁴]	Plastic W [cm ³]
149	9	C14 Conifere. pioppo	560,00	18.666,67	1.866,67

Roof slope

No.	Min quote [cm]	Max quote [cm]	Thickness [cm]	G [N/mm ²]	Ex [N/mm ²]	Ey [N/mm ²]	Mass loading	Type
1	1.540	2.040	-	-	-	-	Unidirectional	Rigid floor
2	1.540	2.040	-	-	-	-	Unidirectional	Rigid floor

• Nodes coordinates

Node	X [cm]	Y [cm]	Z [cm]
1	-1667	697	0
2	-1667	697	560
3	-1667	697	980
4	-1667	697	1380
5	2279	697	0
6	2279	697	560
7	2279	697	980
8	2279	697	1380
9	2316	-917	0
10	2316	-917	560
11	2316	-917	980
12	2316	-917	1380
13	2059	-917	0
14	2059	-917	560
15	2059	-917	980
16	2059	-917	1380
17	-1631	-597	0
18	-1631	-597	560
19	-1631	-597	980
20	-1631	-597	1380
21	2309	-597	0
22	2309	-597	560
23	2309	-597	980
24	2309	-597	1380
25	-1622	-915	0
26	-1622	-915	560
27	-1622	-915	980
28	-1622	-915	1380
29	-1366	-913	0
30	-1366	-913	560
31	-1366	-913	980
32	-1366	-913	1380
33	-1649	27	0
34	-1649	27	560
35	-1649	27	980
36	-1649	27	1380
37	2295	27	0
38	2295	27	560
39	2295	27	980
40	2295	27	1380
41	-1296	-597	0
42	-1296	-597	560
43	-1296	-597	980
44	-1296	-597	1380
45	-1296	697	0
46	-1296	697	560
47	-1296	697	980
48	-1296	697	1380

49	-1296	27	0
50	-1296	27	560
51	-1296	27	980
52	-1296	27	1380
53	-939	-597	0
54	-939	-597	560
55	-939	-597	980
56	-939	-597	1380
57	-939	697	0
58	-939	697	560
59	-939	27	0
60	-939	27	560
61	-939	27	980
62	-939	27	1380
63	-583	27	0
64	-583	27	560
65	-583	27	980
66	-583	27	1380
67	-583	697	0
68	-583	697	560
69	-583	697	980
70	-583	697	1380
71	-483	-597	0
72	-483	-597	560
73	-483	-597	980
74	-483	-597	1380
75	-483	27	0
76	-483	27	560
77	-483	27	980
78	-483	27	1380
79	97	-597	0
80	97	-597	560
81	97	-597	980
82	97	-597	1380
83	97	697	0
84	97	697	560
85	97	697	980
86	97	697	1380
87	97	27	0
88	97	27	560
89	97	27	980
90	97	27	1380
91	505	-597	0
92	505	-597	560
93	505	-597	980
94	505	-597	1380
95	505	697	0
96	505	697	560
97	505	697	980

PRO-SIS

98	505	697	1380
99	505	27	0
100	505	27	560
101	505	27	980
102	505	27	1380
103	1190	-597	0
104	1190	-597	560
105	1190	-597	980
106	1190	-597	1380
107	1190	697	0
108	1190	697	560
109	1190	697	980
110	1190	697	1380
111	1190	27	0
112	1190	27	560
113	1190	27	980
114	1190	27	1380
115	1547	-597	0
116	1547	-597	560
117	1547	-597	980
118	1547	-597	1380
119	1547	697	0
120	1547	697	560
121	1547	697	980
122	1547	697	1380
123	1547	27	0

124	1547	27	560
125	1547	27	980
126	1547	27	1380
127	1910	-597	0
128	1910	-597	560
129	1910	697	0
130	1910	697	560
131	1910	27	0
132	1910	27	560
133	-483	-192	0
134	-483	-192	560
135	-483	-192	980
136	-483	-192	1380
137	97	-192	0
138	97	-192	560
139	97	-192	980
140	97	-192	1380
141	-1366	-597	0
142	-1366	-597	560
143	-1366	-597	980
144	-1366	-597	1380
145	2059	-597	0
146	2059	-597	560
147	2059	-597	980
148	2059	-597	1380

- Piers and spandrel elements**

Wall : 1

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
200	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	164.0	380.0	356	190	45	46
201	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	164.0	380.0	710	190	57	58
202	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	164.0	380.0	1064	190	67	68
203	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	164.0	380.0	1418	190	149	150
206	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	164.0	380.0	2508	190	151	152
207	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	164.0	380.0	2862	190	107	108
208	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	164.0	380.0	3216	190	119	120
209	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	164.0	380.0	3570	190	129	130
204	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	144.0	392.5	1762	196	83	84
205	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	136.0	392.5	2168	196	95	96
199	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	84.5	487.2	42	244	1	2
210	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	104.3	487.2	3895	244	5	6
212	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	356	758	46	47
213	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	710	758	58	153
214	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	1064	758	68	69
215	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	1418	758	150	154
216	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	231.5	220.0	1778	758	84	85
217	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	236.5	220.0	2146	758	96	97
218	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	2508	758	152	155
219	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	2862	758	108	109
220	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	3216	758	120	121
221	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	3570	758	130	156
211	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	112.5	320.0	56	766	2	3
222	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	132.3	320.0	3881	766	6	7
224	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	356	1178	47	48
225	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	710	1178	153	157
226	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	1064	1178	69	70
227	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	1418	1178	154	158
228	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	231.5	220.0	1778	1178	85	86
229	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	236.5	220.0	2146	1178	97	98
230	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	2508	1178	155	159
231	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	2862	1178	109	110
232	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	3216	1178	121	122
233	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	220.0	220.0	3570	1178	156	160
223	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	112.5	310.0	56	1179	3	4
234	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	132.3	310.0	3881	1179	7	8

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
188	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	162.0	180.0	179	470	2	46
189	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	162.0	180.0	533	470	46	58
190	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	162.0	180.0	887	470	58	68
191	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	162.0	180.0	1241	470	68	150
192	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	162.0	180.0	1595	470	150	84
194	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	162.0	180.0	2331	470	96	152
195	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	162.0	180.0	2685	470	152	108
196	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	162.0	180.0	3039	470	108	120
197	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	162.0	180.0	3393	470	120	130
198	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	162.0	180.0	3747	470	130	6
193	FRCM_75	PRO-SIS_1	75.0	200.0	155.0	1964	483	84	96
1	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	162.0	88.0	179	604	2	46
2	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	162.0	88.0	533	604	46	58
3	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	162.0	88.0	887	604	58	68
4	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	162.0	88.0	1241	604	68	150
5	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	162.0	88.0	1595	604	150	84
6	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	200.0	88.0	1964	604	84	96
7	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	162.0	88.0	2331	604	96	152
8	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	162.0	88.0	2685	604	152	108
9	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	162.0	88.0	3039	604	108	120
10	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	162.0	88.0	3393	604	120	130
11	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	162.0	88.0	3747	604	130	6
12	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	179	924	3	47
14	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	533	924	47	153
16	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	887	924	153	69
18	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	1241	924	69	154
20	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	1595	924	154	85
22	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	1961	924	85	97
24	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	2331	924	97	155
26	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	2685	924	155	109
28	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	3039	924	109	121
30	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	3393	924	121	156
32	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	3747	924	156	7
13	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	179	1024	3	47
15	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	533	1024	47	153
17	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	887	1024	153	69
19	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	1241	1024	69	154
21	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	1595	1024	154	85
23	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	1961	1024	85	97
25	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	2331	1024	97	155
27	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	2685	1024	155	109
29	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	3039	1024	109	121
31	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	3393	1024	121	156
33	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	3747	1024	156	7

34	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	179	1334	4	48
35	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	533	1334	48	157
36	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	887	1334	157	70
37	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	1241	1334	70	158
38	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	1595	1334	158	86
39	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	1961	1334	86	98
40	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	2331	1334	98	159
41	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	2685	1334	159	110
42	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	3039	1334	110	122
43	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	3393	1334	122	160
44	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	3747	1334	160	8

Wall : 2

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
235	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	670.1	560.0	335	280	161	162
236	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	624.3	560.0	982	280	163	164
237	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	319.9	560.0	1454	280	165	166
238	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	670.1	420.0	335	770	162	167
239	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	624.3	420.0	982	770	164	168
240	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	319.9	420.0	1454	770	166	169
241	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	670.1	400.0	335	1180	167	170
242	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	624.3	400.0	982	1180	168	171
243	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	319.9	400.0	1454	1180	169	172

Wall : 3

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
45	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	257.3	560.0	129	280	173	174
46	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	257.3	420.0	129	770	174	175
47	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	257.3	400.0	129	1180	175	176

Wall : 4

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
51	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	10.6	490.2	5	245	145	146
52	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	179.2	490.2	230	245	13	14
53	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	9.9	376.8	5	748	146	147
54	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	179.8	376.8	230	748	14	15
55	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	10.0	364.4	5	1162	147	148
56	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	179.7	364.4	230	1162	15	16

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness	Basis	Height	X centre of	Z centre of	Left	Right
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			[cm]	[cm]	[cm]	mass [cm]	mass [cm]	node	node
48	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	130.0	170.0	75	475	146	14
49	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	130.0	100.0	75	930	147	15
50	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	130.0	80.0	75	1340	148	16

Wall : 5

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
250	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	332.3	210.0	3581	105	127	128
245	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	542.6	220.0	460	150	41	42
247	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	176.5	307.5	2154	154	91	92
248	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	599.1	240.0	2652	165	103	104
249	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	242.8	240.0	3183	165	115	116
246	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	924.1	312.5	1338	196	71	72
244	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	73.2	464.1	37	232	17	18
251	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	83.1	464.5	3898	232	21	22
262	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	306.2	215.0	3580	712	128	147
253	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	242.5	220.0	309	714	42	43
263	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	97.3	350.0	3891	735	22	23
252	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	73.2	351.3	37	736	18	19
254	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	176.7	220.0	653	758	54	55
255	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	111.6	220.0	931	758	72	177
258	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	249.8	220.0	2103	758	92	93
259	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	232.5	220.0	2478	758	104	178
260	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	211.1	220.0	2834	758	104	105
261	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	218.8	220.0	3183	758	116	117
256	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	247.2	240.0	1245	768	72	73
257	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	331.0	240.0	1679	768	80	81
274	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	304.0	215.0	3578	1132	147	148
265	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	242.5	220.0	309	1134	43	44
275	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	99.5	334.6	3890	1147	23	24
264	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	73.2	336.1	37	1148	19	20
266	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	176.7	220.0	653	1178	55	56
267	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	111.6	220.0	931	1178	177	179
270	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	249.8	220.0	2103	1178	93	94
271	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	232.5	220.0	2478	1178	178	180
272	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	211.1	220.0	2834	1178	105	106
273	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	218.8	220.0	3183	1178	117	118
268	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	247.2	250.0	1245	1193	73	74
269	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	331.0	250.0	1679	1193	81	82

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
58	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	145.0	80.0	803	40	53	71
65	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	110.0	90.0	3007	45	103	115

63	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	122.0	350.0	2296	385	92	104
68	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	122.0	350.0	3359	385	116	128
70	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	110.0	350.0	3795	385	146	22
57	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	115.0	340.0	131	390	18	142
59	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	139.5	260.0	806	430	54	72
66	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	122.0	200.0	3007	460	104	116
61	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	200.0	155.0	1922	483	80	92
60	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	139.5	88.0	806	604	54	72
62	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	200.0	88.0	1922	604	80	92
64	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	122.0	88.0	2296	604	92	104
67	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	122.0	88.0	3007	604	104	116
69	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	122.0	88.0	3359	604	116	128
90	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	110.0	210.0	3787	875	147	23
71	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	115.0	200.0	131	880	19	143
72	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	498	924	43	55
74	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	808	924	55	177
76	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	1054	924	177	73
80	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	1911	924	81	93
82	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	2295	924	93	178
84	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	2662	924	178	105
86	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	3007	924	105	117
88	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	112.0	3359	924	117	147
78	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	145.0	72.0	1441	944	73	81
73	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	498	1024	43	55
75	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	808	1024	55	177
77	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	1054	1024	177	73
79	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	145.0	88.0	1441	1024	73	81
81	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	1911	1024	81	93
83	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	2295	1024	93	178
85	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	2662	1024	178	105
87	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	3007	1024	105	117
89	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	3359	1024	117	147
101	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	110.0	190.0	3785	1285	148	24
91	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	115.0	180.0	131	1290	20	144
92	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	498	1334	44	56
93	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	808	1334	56	179
94	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	1054	1334	179	74
96	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	1911	1334	82	94
97	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	2295	1334	94	180
98	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	2662	1334	180	106
99	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	3007	1334	106	118
100	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	134.0	92.0	3359	1334	118	148
95	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	145.0	32.0	1441	1364	74	82

Wall : 6

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
276	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	670.2	560.0	335	280	181	182
277	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	624.3	560.0	982	280	183	184
278	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	318.4	560.0	1454	280	185	186
279	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	670.2	420.0	335	770	182	187
280	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	624.3	420.0	982	770	184	188
281	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	318.4	420.0	1454	770	186	189
282	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	670.2	400.0	335	1180	187	190
283	FRCM_45i	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	624.3	400.0	982	1180	188	191
284	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	318.4	400.0	1454	1180	189	192

Wall : 7

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
102	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	256.7	560.0	128	280	193	194
103	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	256.7	420.0	128	770	194	195
104	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	256.7	400.0	128	1180	195	196

Wall : 8

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
291	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	238.0	220.0	350	110	49	50
292	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	238.4	220.0	703	110	59	60
293	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	592.8	220.0	1234	110	75	76
296	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	195.5	220.0	2861	110	111	112
297	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	244.4	220.0	3193	110	123	124
298	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	239.1	220.0	3551	110	131	132
294	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	173.3	312.5	1731	156	87	88
295	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	564.6	312.5	2366	156	99	100
290	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	116.1	464.1	58	232	33	34
299	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	161.9	464.1	3862	232	37	38
118	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	616.4	220.0	527	670	50	51
119	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	406.8	220.0	1128	670	76	77
122	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	219.0	220.0	2860	670	112	113
120	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	413.6	295.0	1629	708	88	89
121	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	585.3	295.0	2368	708	100	101
117	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	128.6	351.3	64	736	34	35
123	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	883.5	351.3	3501	736	132	125
125	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	603.9	220.0	521	1090	51	52
126	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	382.3	220.0	1129	1090	77	78
129	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	219.0	220.0	2860	1090	113	114
127	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	401.6	285.0	1635	1123	89	90

128	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	585.3	285.0	2368	1123	101	102
124	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	128.6	336.1	64	1148	35	36
130	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	883.5	336.1	3501	1148	125	126

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
285	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	102.5	340.0	174	390	34	50
286	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	102.5	340.0	880	390	60	64
288	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	102.5	340.0	2706	390	100	112
289	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	101.0	340.0	3015	390	112	124
287	FRCM_60	PRO-SIS_1	60.0	253.0	155.0	1953	483	88	100
105	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	90.0	200.0	174	880	35	51
106	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	102.5	200.0	880	880	61	65
107	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	102.0	200.0	1377	880	77	89
109	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	90.0	200.0	2706	880	101	113
110	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	90.0	200.0	3015	880	113	125
108	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	240.0	50.0	1955	955	89	101
111	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	90.0	180.0	174	1290	36	52
112	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	115.0	180.0	880	1290	62	66
113	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	114.0	180.0	1377	1290	78	90
115	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	90.0	180.0	2706	1290	102	114
116	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	90.0	180.0	3015	1290	114	126
114	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	60.0	240.0	50.0	1955	1355	90	102

Wall : 9

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
300	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	30.0	1294.0	560.0	647	280	49	50
302	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	662.7	220.0	541	670	50	51
301	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	120.0	351.3	60	736	42	43
303	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	287.3	351.3	1150	736	46	47
136	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	662.7	220.0	541	1090	51	52
135	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	120.0	336.1	60	1148	43	44
137	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	287.3	336.1	1150	1148	47	48

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
131	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	90.0	200.0	165	880	43	51
132	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	134.0	200.0	940	880	51	47
133	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	90.0	180.0	165	1290	44	52
134	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	134.0	180.0	940	1290	52	48

Wall : 10

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
305	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	30.0	624.1	560.0	312	280	197	198
139	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	669.9	560.0	959	280	199	200
306	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	119.7	351.3	60	736	54	55
307	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	414.4	351.3	417	736	198	61
140	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	123.7	336.1	62	1148	55	56
141	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	410.4	336.1	419	1148	61	62

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
304	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	90.0	200.0	167	880	55	61
138	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	90.0	180.0	169	1290	56	62

Wall : 11

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
309	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	30.0	669.9	560.0	335	280	201	202
310	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	263.6	351.3	132	736	64	65
311	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	272.3	351.3	534	736	68	69
143	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	263.6	336.1	132	1148	65	66
144	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	272.3	336.1	534	1148	69	70

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
308	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	134.0	200.0	331	880	65	69
142	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	134.0	180.0	331	1290	66	70

Wall : 12

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
314	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_2	45.0	624.1	560.0	312	280	133	134
315	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_2	45.0	435.5	396.6	218	758	134	135
316	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_2	45.0	28.6	396.6	610	758	76	77
317	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	435.5	376.7	218	1168	135	136
318	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	28.6	376.7	610	1168	77	78

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
312	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_2	45.0	160.0	50.0	515	955	135	77

313	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	160.0	50.0	515	1355	136	78
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Wall : 13

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
152	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	77.9	484.4	39	242	79	80
153	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	289.2	484.4	480	242	137	138
320	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	669.9	560.0	959	280	203	204
155	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	103.7	370.0	387	745	138	139
154	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	77.9	396.6	39	758	80	81
156	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	25.5	396.6	611	758	88	89
321	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	22.9	320.0	636	766	88	89
322	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	513.0	320.0	1038	766	204	85
158	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	103.7	350.0	387	1155	139	140
159	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	48.4	285.0	623	1167	89	90

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
145	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	257.0	190.0	206	465	80	138
319	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	134.0	112.0	714	924	89	85
146	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	257.0	50.0	206	955	81	139
147	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	160.0	50.0	519	955	139	89
148	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	88.0	714	1024	89	85
151	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	134.0	92.0	714	1334	90	86
149	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	257.0	50.0	206	1355	82	140
150	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	45.0	160.0	50.0	519	1355	140	90

Wall : 14

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
325	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	1294.0	560.0	647	280	99	100
327	FRCM_30-1	PRO-SIS_1	30.0	327.1	220.0	735	670	100	101
326	FRCM_30-1	PRO-SIS_1	30.0	437.9	351.3	219	736	92	93
328	FRCM_30-1	PRO-SIS_1	30.0	261.0	351.3	1164	736	96	97
164	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	327.1	220.0	735	1090	101	102
163	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	437.9	336.1	219	1148	93	94
165	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	261.0	336.1	1164	1148	97	98
325	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	1294.0	560.0	647	280	99	100

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
323	FRCM_30-1	PRO-SIS_1	30.0	134.0	200.0	505	880	93	101
324	FRCM_30-1	PRO-SIS_1	30.0	134.0	200.0	966	880	101	97

161	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	134.0	180.0	505	1290	94	102
162	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	134.0	180.0	966	1290	102	98

Wall : 15

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
332	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	30.0	1294.0	560.0	647	280	111	112
334	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	227.8	220.0	324	670	112	205
335	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	375.0	220.0	715	670	112	113
333	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	120.1	351.3	60	736	104	105
336	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	257.1	351.3	1165	736	108	109
170	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	227.8	220.0	324	1090	205	206
171	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	375.0	220.0	715	1090	113	114
169	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	120.1	336.1	60	1148	105	106
172	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	257.1	336.1	1165	1148	109	110

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
329	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	90.0	200.0	165	880	105	205
330	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	90.0	200.0	483	880	205	113
331	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	134.0	200.0	970	880	113	109
166	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	90.0	180.0	165	1290	106	206
167	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	90.0	180.0	483	1290	206	114
168	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	134.0	180.0	970	1290	114	110

Wall : 16

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
339	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	30.0	1294.0	560.0	647	280	123	124
340	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	120.1	351.3	60	736	116	117
341	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	414.0	351.3	417	736	124	125
342	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2d	15.0	277.2	351.3	763	736	124	125
343	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2d	15.0	258.7	351.3	1165	736	120	121
176	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	691.2	220.0	556	1090	125	126
175	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	120.1	336.1	60	1148	117	118
177	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	258.7	336.1	1165	1148	121	122
339	FRCM_30-2	PRO-SIS_2	30.0	1294.0	560.0	647	280	123	124

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
337	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2	15.0	90.0	200.0	165	880	117	125
338	FRCM_15-2	PRO-SIS_2d	15.0	134.0	200.0	968	880	125	121
173	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	90.0	180.0	165	1290	118	126

174	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	15.0	134.0	180.0	968	1290	126	122
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Wall : 17

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
178	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	1294.0	560.0	647	280	131	132

Wall : 18

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
347	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	35.9	464.1	474	232	133	134
348	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	435.9	464.1	818	232	137	138
349	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	44.9	351.3	478	736	134	135
350	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	444.9	351.3	813	736	138	139
351	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	44.9	336.1	478	1148	135	136
352	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	444.9	336.1	813	1148	139	140

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
344	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	99.0	340.0	546	390	134	138
345	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	45.0	90.0	200.0	546	880	135	139
346	FRCM_45	PRO-SIS_1	15.0	90.0	180.0	546	1290	136	140

Wall : 19

Pier macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Top node	Bottom node
182	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	175.5	490.2	88	245	29	30
183	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	10.3	490.2	311	245	141	142
184	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	176.0	376.8	88	748	30	31
185	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	9.9	376.8	311	748	142	143
186	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	175.8	364.4	88	1162	31	32
187	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	10.0	364.4	311	1162	143	144

Spandrel beam macroelements

No.	Material	Reinforcement	Thickness [cm]	Basis [cm]	Height [cm]	X centre of mass [cm]	Z centre of mass [cm]	Left node	Right node
179	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	130.0	170.0	241	475	30	142
180	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	130.0	100.0	241	930	31	143
181	old_brick_Ljubljana	-	30.0	130.0	80.0	241	1340	32	144

3.4.2. Modal analysis

Results of modal analysis are shown in the Table 3.1: natural periods (T) and contribution to masses in X and Y direction (Mx, My). First 10 modal shapes cover over 95% of structure mass.

Table 3.1 Masonry material characteristics for building – CRM strengthened configuration

Mode	T [s]	mx [kg]	Mx [%]	my [kg]	My [%]	mz [kg]	Mz [%]
1	0.379	37119	1.29	2147597	74.77	819	0.03
2	0.350	1596225	55.57	87522	3.05	107	0
3	0.325	830359	28.91	10657	0.37	14	0
4	0.219	1636	0.06	30487	1.06	749	0.03
5	0.165	3	0	478327	16.65	466	0.02
6	0.150	8258	0.29	4247	0.15	14048	0.49
7	0.148	1983	0.07	5072	0.18	1287	0.04
8	0.143	537	0.02	255	0.01	499	0.02
9	0.129	145370	5.06	934	0.03	272	0.01
10	0.127	125298	4.36	5434	0.19	348	0.01
sum		2746788	95.63	2770532	96.46	18609	0.65

Modal shapes for first two X and Y and first rotational shape are shown on the following figures.

Fig. 3.6 1st modal shape (translatory in Y direction, almost linear over height)

Fig. 3.7 2nd modal shape (mostly translatory in X direction, linear over height)

Fig. 3.8 3rd modal shape (rotational, linear over height)

Fig. 3.9 5th modal shape (second tone in Y direction)

3.5. Global analysis of the CRM strengthened structure

3.5.1. Analysis characteristics

The same analysis characteristics adopted for the unreinforced building described in PRO-SIS Report 3.3 [1] were considered.

3.5.2. Results

Below are presented results of pushover analysis; marked with yellow are the critical cases for each main direction X, Y. Structure should have $\zeta_B = dm/dt \geq 1$ (capacity \geq demand).

The results show that capacity of the structure, depending on the direction of earthquake and eccentricity, fulfil between 100% and 218% of the earthquake demand. Therefore the proposed structural strengthening was sufficient. The improvement of CRM strengthened building over URM is also presented – showing improvement from 1.3 to 4.6, depending on the analysis parameters.

N.	Seism dir.	Seismic load	Ecc. [cm]	CRM STRENGTHENED			UNSTRENGTHENED			INCR. ζ_B NC	ζ_B NC
				dt NC [mm]	dm NC [mm]	ζ_B NC	dt NC [mm]	dm NC [mm]	ζ_B NC		
1	+X	Uniform	0	61.7	99.4	1.61	98.42	61.13	0.62	2.51	0.62
2	+X	Static forces	0	74.9	78.5	1.05	107.73	88.1	0.82	1.24	0.82
3	-X	Uniforme	0	61.5	131.7	2.14	95.29	44.29	0.46	5.36	0.46
4	-X	Static forces	0	71.4	125.0	1.75	103.89	74.29	0.72	1.59	0.72
5	+Y	Uniforme	0	41.0	66.7	1.63	74.99	46.58	0.62	2.47	0.62
6	+Y	Static forces	0	50.9	79.6	1.56	87.68	49.6	0.57	2.72	0.57
7	-Y	Uniform	0	46.9	60.2	1.28	87.94	51.21	0.58	2.42	0.58
8	-Y	Static forces	0	58.9	58.9	1.00	99.61	59.28	0.60	2.04	0.60
9	+X	Uniform	80.7	64.2	92.5	1.44	98.81	100.76	1.02	1.56	1.02
10	+X	Uniform	-80.7	67.6	97.3	1.44	97.41	105.33	1.08	1.39	1.08
11	+X	Static forces	80.7	70.9	78.4	1.10	108.19	87.76	0.81	1.22	0.81
12	+X	Static forces	-80.7	72.3	78.6	1.09	108.54	87.74	0.81	1.26	0.81
13	-X	Uniform	80.7	59.7	130.1	2.18	93.31	44.53	0.48	5.15	0.48
14	-X	Uniform	-80.7	62.3	131.0	2.10	97.00	44.05	0.45	3.17	0.45
15	-X	Static forces	80.7	69.7	123.4	1.77	103.41	65.5	0.63	1.66	0.63
16	-X	Static forces	-80.7	70.0	123.6	1.76	103.43	67.88	0.66	1.68	0.66
17	+Y	Uniform	199.2	40.8	66.7	1.64	74.81	42.4	0.57	2.41	0.57
18	+Y	Uniform	-199.2	43.2	66.2	1.53	75.73	43.75	0.58	2.53	0.58
19	+Y	Static forces	199.2	49.8	58.0	1.16	85.19	41.56	0.49	2.58	0.49
20	+Y	Static forces	-199.2	51.7	58.6	1.13	88.4	43.56	0.49	2.98	0.49
21	-Y	Uniform	199.2	46.3	47.4	1.02	86.83	43.96	0.51	3.50	0.51
22	-Y	Uniform	-199.2	47.0	55.3	1.18	86.98	46.01	0.53	2.59	0.53
23	-Y	Static forces	199.2	57.3	58.3	1.02	98.76	45.69	0.46	2.45	0.46
24	-Y	Static forces	-199.2	58.2	58.2	1.00	99.78	48.29	0.48	2.15	0.48

The capacity curves of the building in the two main directions are shown below. With 24 listed analyses, considering two different load distribution (fundamental vibration mode / masses over height distribution), positive and negative direction of earthquake action and accidental eccentricity (or without).

Fig. 3.10 Push over envelopes for X direction (different eccentricities, \pm seismic directions).
Red curve is for the critical analysis in X direction (#8)

Fig. 3.11 Push over envelopes for Y direction (different eccentricities, \pm seismic directions).
Red curve is for the critical analysis in Y direction (#2)

For lowest LS (Life safety) cases (analysis no.2 for X direction and no.8 for Y direction) the damage distribution for some walls is presented on the following figures. The shape of structure deformation and capacity curve is shown. Distribution of damage corresponds to the marked step on their capacity curve. Results in such manner can be produced for all analyses on the list and all walls, for all steps of analysis (of interest) on the capacity curve.

Results legend - masonry

• **Seismic analysis n. 2 Direction X (worst case for X direction)**

Fig. 3.12 Seismic analysis n. 2 Wall 1 (street wall)

Fig. 3.13 Seismic analysis n. 2 Wall 8 (middle wall)

Fig. 3.14 Seismic analysis n. 2 Wall 5 (back wall)

Fig. 3.15 3D representation of damage distribution on structure elements for analysis no.2.

- **Seismic analysis n. 8 Direction Y (worst case for y direction)**

Fig. 3.16 Seismic analysis n. 8 Wall 9

Fig. 3.17 Seismic analysis n. 8 Wall 14

Fig. 3.18 Seismic analysis n. 8 Wall 15

Fig. 3.19 Seismic analysis n. 8 Wall 16

Fig. 3.20 3D representation of damage distribution on structure elements for analysis no.8

3.6. Structural drawing of the intervention

The structural drawing of the strengthening intervention are included in ANNEX C of this Report.

3.7. Cost estimation of the reinforcement intervention

The bill of quantities of the strengthening intervention is included in ANNEX D of this Report.

Acknowledgments

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ANNEX A - Structural drawings of the building of ATER in Udine – CRM strengthened status

FLOOR -1
Scale 1:50

1st FLOOR
Scale 1:50

MATERIALS PRESCRIPTION

PREFORMED GFRP MESH:

- mesh 66x66,
- number of wires each meter: 15,
- minimum characteristic tensile force: 4.36 kN
- maximum ultimate elongation: 1.78%,
- elastic modulus: 25000 N/mm²,
- CE certified about EAD 34.0392-00-0104

PREFORMED GFRP ANGULAR MESH:

- mesh 66x66,
- number of wires each meter: 15,
- minimum characteristic tensile force: 4.36 kN
- maximum ultimate elongation: 1.78%,
- elastic modulus: 25000 N/mm²,
- CE certified about EAD 34.0392-00-0104
- side dimension 30 cm

PREFORMED GFRP "L" SHAPE CONNECTOR:

- minimum section: 7x10 cm,
- characteristic tensile force: 380 N/mm²,
- nominal fiber area: 32.4 mm².

ANCHOR RESIN:

- type of resin: vinylstere
- cleaning the holes with compressed air

STAINLESS STEEL AISI 316:

- characteristic yield strength: $f_{yk} \geq 235 \text{ N/mm}^2$,
- characteristic ultimate strength: $f_{tk} \geq 500 \text{ N/mm}^2$,

BARNS AND NUTS CLASS A4-70

- characteristic yield strength: $f_{yb} \geq 450 \text{ N/mm}^2$,
- characteristic ultimate strength: $f_{tb} \geq 700 \text{ N/mm}^2$,

LIME BASED MORTAR M10

- compressive strength - 28 days: 10 N/mm²,
- qualified by EN 998-2,

CEMENTITIOUS BASED MORTAR M25:

- compressive strength - 28 days: 25 N/mm²,
- qualified by EN 998-2

Measure in cm (unless otherwise specified)

SECTION 1-1
Scale 1:100

SECTION 2-2
Scale 1:50

DETAIL J
Scale 1:10

MATERIALS PRESCRIPTION:

PREFORMED GFRP MESH:

- mesh: 66x66;
- number of wires each meter: 15;
- minimum characteristic tensile force: 4.36 kN
- maximum ultimate elongation: 1.78%;
- elastic modulus: 25000 N/mm²;
- CE certified about EAD 340392-00-0104

PREFORMED GFRP ANGULAR MESH:

- mesh: 66x66;
- number of wires each meter: 15;
- minimum characteristic tensile force: 4.36 kN
- maximum ultimate elongation: 1.78%;
- elastic modulus: 25000 N/mm²;
- CE certified about EAD 340392-00-0104
- side dimension: 30 cm

PREFORMED GFRP "L" SHAPE CONNECTOR:

- minimum section: 7x10 cm;
- characteristic tensile force: 380 N/mm²;
- nominal fiber area: 32.4 mm².

ANCHOR RESIN:

- type of resin: vinyl ester
- cleaning the holes with compressed air

STAINLESS STEEL AISI 316:

- characteristic yield strength: $f_{yk} \geq 235N/mm^2$;
- characteristic ultimate strength: $f_{tk} \geq 500N/mm^2$;

BARS AND NUTS CLASS A4-70:

- characteristic yield strength: $f_{yb} \geq 450 N/mm^2$;
- characteristic ultimate strength: $f_{tb} \geq 700 N/mm^2$;

LIME BASED MORTAR M10:

- compressive strength - 28 days: 10 N/mm²;
- qualified by EN 998-2;

CEMENTITIOUS BASED MORTAR M25:

- compressive strength - 28 days: 25 N/mm²;
- qualified by EN 998-2.

Measure in cm (unless otherwise specified)

SECTION 3-3
Scale 1:50

BACK FAÇADE
Scale 1:50

SIDE FAÇADE
Scale 1:50

FRONT FAÇADE
Scale 1:50

- MATERIALS PRESCRIPTION:**
- PREFORMED GFRP MESH:**
 - mesh: 66x66;
 - number of wires each meter: 15;
 - minimum characteristic tensile force: 4.36 kN
 - maximum ultimate elongation: 1.78%;
 - elastic modulus: 25000 N/mm²;
 - CE certified about EAD 34.0392-00-0104
 - PREFORMED GFRP ANGULAR MESH:**
 - mesh: 66x66;
 - number of wires each meter: 15;
 - minimum characteristic tensile force: 4.36 kN
 - maximum ultimate elongation: 1.78%;
 - elastic modulus: 25000 N/mm²;
 - CE certified about EAD 34.0392-00-0104
 - side dimension: 30 cm
 - PREFORMED GFRP "L" SHAPE CONNECTOR:**
 - minimum section: 7x10 cm;
 - characteristic tensile force: 380 N/mm²;
 - nominal fiber area: 32.4 mm².
 - ANCHOR RESIN:**
 - type of resin: vinylstere
 - cleaning the holes with compressed air
 - STAINLESS STEEL AISI 316:**
 - characteristic yield strength: $f_{yk} \geq 235 \text{ N/mm}^2$;
 - characteristic ultimate strength: $f_{tk} \geq 500 \text{ N/mm}^2$;
 - BARS AND NUTS CLASS A4-70:**
 - characteristic yield strength: $f_{yb} \geq 450 \text{ N/mm}^2$;
 - characteristic ultimate strength: $f_{tb} \geq 700 \text{ N/mm}^2$;
 - LIME BASED MORTAR M10:**
 - compressive strength - 28 days: 10 N/mm²;
 - qualified by EN 998-2;
 - CEMENTITIOUS BASED MORTAR M25:**
 - compressive strength - 28 days: 25 N/mm²;
 - qualified by EN 998-2.
- Measure in cm (unless otherwise specified)

DETAIL A
Scale 1:10

DETAIL B
Scale 1:10

DETAIL C
Scale 1:10

DETAIL K
Scale 1:10

DETAIL D
Scale 1:10

DETAIL E
Scale 1:10

DETAIL F
Scale 1:10

DETAIL G
Scale 1:10

DETAIL H
Scale 1:10

DETAIL L
Scale 1:20

MATERIALS PRESCRIPTION:

- PREFORMED GFRP MESH:**
 - mesh: 66x66;
 - number of wires each meter: 15;
 - minimum characteristic tensile force: 4.36 kN
 - maximum ultimate elongation: 1.78%;
 - elastic modulus: 25000 N/mm²;
 - CE certified about EAD 340392-00-0104
- PREFORMED GFRP ANGULAR MESH:**
 - mesh: 66x66;
 - number of wires each meter: 15;
 - minimum characteristic tensile force: 4.36 kN
 - maximum ultimate elongation: 1.78%;
 - elastic modulus: 25000 N/mm²;
 - CE certified about EAD 340392-00-0104
 - side dimension: 30 cm
- PREFORMED GFRP "L" SHAPE CONNECTOR:**
 - minimum section: 7x10 cm;
 - characteristic tensile force: 380 N/mm²;
 - nominal fiber area: 32.4 mm².
- ANCHOR RESIN:**
 - type of resin: vinyl estere
 - cleaning the holes with compressed air
- STAINLESS STEEL AISI 316:**
 - characteristic yield strength: $f_{yk} \geq 235N/mm^2$;
 - characteristic ultimate strength: $f_{tk} \geq 500N/mm^2$;
- BARS AND NUTS CLASS A4-70:**
 - characteristic yield strength: $f_{yb} \geq 450 N/mm^2$;
 - characteristic ultimate strength: $f_{tb} \geq 700 N/mm^2$;
- LIME BASED MORTAR M10:**
 - compressive strength - 28 days: 10 N/mm²;
 - qualified by EN 998-2;
- CEMENTITIUS BASED MORTAR M25:**
 - compressive strength - 28 days: 25 N/mm²;
 - qualified by EN 998-2.

Measure in cm (unless otherwise specified)

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX B - Bill of quantities for the strengthening of the building of ATER in Udine by using the CONSTRAIN-PROSIS technology

From Italian price analysis

N.	CODE	DESCRIPTION OF WORKS AND SUPPLIES	UNIT	SIMILAR	LENGTH	WIDTH	HEIGHT	QUANTITY	PRICE	AMOUNT
	L1	WORKS ABOVE GROUND								
	02	Structural works								
1	20.6.HH2.09	GALVANIZED STEEL COMPONENTS FOR LIGHT METALWORK, WITH WEIGHT BELOW 20 kg/m Prefabricated steel components for railings, guardrails, and similar items; for stairs and doors of all sizes; walkways with a unit weight below 20 kg/m, manufactured according to the drawings and specifications provided by the Site Supervisor, constructed using tubular steel sections with circular, square, or rectangular profiles; flat, square, and round bars; L-, T-, U-, and Z-shaped sections; electro-welded gratings and steel sheets for cladding and pedestrian walkways. Supplied and installed including: hot-dip galvanizing upon completion of fabrication; cutting waste; hardware for hinges and handles; locks; transport to the place of installation; unloading and installation at any height, including on-site welding; masonry work support; and all other related services, supplies, and charges.								
		<i>Reinforcement saddles for RC beams in terrace areas</i>	Kg	420.00				420.00		
		Total	Kg					420.00	€ 14.67	€ 6 161.40
2	PA.02 (see the attached detailed price analysis)	<p>STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - One-sided for single-leaf masonry One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Extrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%. - GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a Ø12 mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments <3%. - Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection; - Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent. <p>The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.</p> <p>EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements. Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.</p> <p>Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.</p>								
		<i>EXTERNAL WALLS</i>								
		<i>West Elevation – Front</i>	m2		34.04		9.88	336.32		
		<i>To be deducted</i>	m2					0.00		
		<i>Terraces</i>	m2	4.00	2.45		9.80	-96.04		
		<i>To be added</i>	m2					0.00		
		<i>East Elevation – Rear</i>	m2		34.04		9.88	336.32		
		<i>North Elevation</i>	m2		9.03		9.88	89.22		
		<i>South Elevation</i>	m2		9.03		9.88	89.22		
		<i>INTERNAL WALLS</i>								
		<i>Above-ground floors</i>	m2	3.00	15.88		2.93	139.59		
		Total	m2					894.61	€ 129.47	€ 115 824.95

L2		BELOW-GROUND WORKS								
01		Excavations and backfilling								
	11.7.CP1.01	FOUNDATION EXCAVATION IN SOIL OF ANY NATURE Execution of foundation excavation in a restricted section in soil of any nature and consistency, including boulders with a volume of less than 0.5 m ³ , excluding soft rock and hard rock requiring blasting, whether dry or wet, also in the presence of water of any type, origin, and quantity, for the construction of foundations for structures in general and building foundations, for the laying of pipelines and prefabricated elements, carried out to depths of up to 2 m relative to the stripping level, including the removal of shrubs and stumps, topsoil stripping and recovery, water pumping, any necessary shoring and bracing of the sides, formation of slopes where required, loading and transport within the site of suitable excavated material, including topsoil, for backfilling and embankments, properly shaped and compacted. Any additional operations for the reuse of excavated material or the removal of material deemed unsuitable by the Works Supervisor shall be compensated separately.								
14	11.7.CP1.01.A	Also in the presence of water (water depth up to 20 cm).								
			WEST side	m3	1.79	34.04			60.86	
			EST side	m3	1.79	34.04			60.86	
			NORTH side	m3	1.79	9.03			16.15	
			SOUTH side	m3	1.79	9.03			16.15	
			Total	m3					154.02	€ 20.19 € 3 109.63
	11.7.CP1.06	MANUAL FOUNDATION EXCAVATION IN SOIL OF ANY NATURE INSIDE BUILDINGS Execution of manual excavation for the construction of foundations for structures in general and for the laying of pipelines inside buildings, in soil of any nature and consistency, including boulders up to 0.5 m ³ and soft rock removable with pick or point tools, excluding hard rock requiring blasting, whether dry or wet, also in the presence of water of any type, origin, and quantity, for depths up to 2 m from the excavation level. This includes shoring and bracing of the sides, preservation and protection of any existing installations such as pipelines, ducts, cables, structures, archaeological finds, etc., formation of slopes, and backfilling. Any additional operations for the reuse of excavated material or the removal of material deemed unsuitable by the Works Supervisor shall be compensated separately.								
15	11.7.CP1.06.A	Also in the presence of water (water depth up to 20 cm).								
			EAST lateral rooms	m3	2.00	3.36	3.97	2.10	56.02	
			WEST lateral rooms	m3	2.00	3.91	3.96	2.10	65.03	
				m3	2.00	1.15	1.66	2.10	8.02	
			EAST central rooms	m3	2.00	3.01	3.97	2.10	50.19	
			WEST central rooms	m3	2.00	3.91	3.96	2.10	65.03	
				m3	2.00	1.15	1.66	2.10	8.02	
			Total	m3					252.31	€ 145.25 € 36 648.20
	11.8.CP1.12	DELIVERY OF EXCAVATED MATERIAL FROM THE SITE TO AUTHORIZED TREATMENT AND RECOVERY FACILITIES Transport and delivery of inert waste material resulting from site activities to an authorized waste treatment and recovery facility, including all administrative requirements for handling, transport within a distance of up to 15 km, and delivery to the treatment plant (waste to be delivered to facilities authorized for treatment in accordance with current regulations, Legislative Decree 152/06 as amended and supplemented, and Regional Law 30/87 as amended and supplemented).								
			see item n. 15	m3	252.31				252.31	
			Total	m3					252.31	€ 46.17 € 11 649.25
		Total Excavations and Backfilling								€ 51 407.08

02		Structural works								
17	PA.03.1 (see the attached detailed price analysis)	<p>STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Two-sided with steel ties</p> <p>Two-sided structural reinforcement of concrete walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, metal connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBMesh66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textursion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%. - Stainless steel connectors for transverse connections, at a rate of 6/m², consisting of M8 threaded rods passing through Ø12 holes, with 50x1.5 mm washer and nut, grade 8.8, at both wall sides. - Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection; - Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent. <p>The system is completed with premixed hydraulic cement mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 5 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 25 MPa.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.</p> <p>EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements. Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.</p> <p>Application on both faces of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.</p>								
		<i>Exterior walls</i>								
		<i>Wall – east side</i>	<i>m2</i>		<i>34.04</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>71.48</i>		
		<i>Wall – west side</i>	<i>m2</i>		<i>34.04</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>71.48</i>		
		<i>Wall – north side</i>	<i>m2</i>		<i>9.03</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>18.96</i>		
		<i>Wall – south side</i>	<i>m2</i>		<i>9.03</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>18.96</i>		
		<i>Interior walls</i>								
		<i>Central wall – long side</i>	<i>m2</i>	<i>2.00</i>	<i>12.52</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>52.58</i>		
		<i>Central walls – short side – opposite staircases</i>	<i>m2</i>	<i>4.00</i>	<i>3.97</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>33.35</i>		
			<i>m2</i>	<i>4.00</i>	<i>2.97</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>24.95</i>		
		<i>Walls – stair side</i>	<i>m2</i>	<i>4.00</i>	<i>3.36</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>28.22</i>		
			<i>m2</i>	<i>4.00</i>	<i>5.66</i>		<i>2.10</i>	<i>47.54</i>		
		<i>Total</i>	<i>m2</i>					<i>367.54</i>	<i>€ 269.11</i>	<i>€ 98 909.23</i>

18	PA.04	<p>STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Surcharge for corner connection Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria). Surcharge for the execution of connections at masonry corners, by using the corner element FBANG66X66T96 by Fibrenet, or equivalent, featuring CE marking, preformed with a 90° bend, consisting of a square mesh with 66x66 mm openings, manufactured with Alkali-Resistant glass roving and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with nominal strand diameter exceeding 3 mm and a width of 33 cm per side. Tensile strength of the composite ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of the individual bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile modulus of elasticity $\geq 25,000$ N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of the individual bar ≥ 4.14 kN, average elongation at failure 1.78%, characteristic node tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity in humid, alkaline, and saline environments $< 8\%$.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: All that is necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with best practice. EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment required for the execution of the work, any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and anything else not specified.</p> <p>The price applies per linear meter.</p>									
			<i>External vertical corners – below ground</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>4.00</i>			<i>2.10</i>	<i>8.40</i>		
			<i>Internal vertical corners – basement</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>68.00</i>			<i>2.10</i>	<i>142.80</i>		
			<i>Total</i>	<i>m</i>					<i>151.20</i>	<i>€ 26.41</i>	<i>€ 3 993.19</i>
19	PA.05	<p>STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors, and across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria). Surcharge for the execution of the connections of the CRM system with the foundation and across floors, as well as across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections, by using M8 stainless steel threaded bars in $\varnothing 12$ diameter holes, and thermosetting vinylesterepoxy resin, applied at a rate of 3/m. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length $50\varnothing$).</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent. EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents., and any other items not specified.</p> <p>The price applies per linear meter.</p>									
			<i>Exterior walls</i>								
			<i>Wall – east side</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>2.00</i>	<i>34.04</i>			<i>68.08</i>		
			<i>Wall – west side</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>2.00</i>	<i>34.04</i>			<i>68.08</i>		
			<i>Wall – north side</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>2.00</i>	<i>9.03</i>			<i>18.06</i>		
			<i>Wall – south side</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>2.00</i>	<i>9.03</i>			<i>18.06</i>		
			<i>Interior walls - connection with foundations</i>								
			<i>Central wall – long side</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>4.00</i>	<i>12.52</i>			<i>50.08</i>		
			<i>Central walls – short side – opposite staircases</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>8.00</i>	<i>3.97</i>			<i>31.76</i>		
				<i>m</i>	<i>8.00</i>	<i>2.97</i>			<i>23.76</i>		
			<i>Walls – stair side</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>8.00</i>	<i>3.36</i>			<i>26.88</i>		
				<i>m</i>	<i>8.00</i>	<i>5.66</i>			<i>45.28</i>		
			<i>Total</i>	<i>m</i>					<i>350.04</i>	<i>€ 35.20</i>	<i>€ 12 321.41</i>
			Total structural works								€ 115 223.83
	03	Building works									
	13.3.LN7.01	WATERPROOFING OF WALLS – PROTECTION WITH DRAINAGE SHEET Supply and installation of a drainage sheet for the protection of waterproofing, including fixing and overlaps.									
20	13.3.LN7.01.A	Drainage sheet 8 mm thick									
			<i>Protection layer – Studded membrane</i>	<i>m2</i>	<i>151.60</i>				<i>151.60</i>		
			<i>Total</i>	<i>m2</i>					<i>151.60</i>	<i>€ 17.00</i>	<i>€ 2 577.20</i>

			-	1.00				1.00		
			Total	-				1.00	€ 743.82	€ 743.82
33	99.1.XB1.01.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first								
			/ month	5.00				5.00		
			Total	/ month				5.00	€ 280.51	€ 1 402.55
	99.1.XB1.05	CONSTRUCTION SITE BOX FOR SANITARY FACILITIES DIM. 2.4 × 2.7 × 2.4 m Supply and installation of a construction site box for sanitary facilities, consisting of a base structure elevated from the ground with folded steel profiles, roof and cladding with sandwich panels made of inner and outer sheet metal and central insulation (minimum 40 mm), internal partitions in sandwich panels, aluminum fixtures, wooden floor covered with PVC. Complete with electrical, water (hot and cold), and sewage systems, electric heating and cooling, equipped with one shower, one WC, one washbasin, electric boiler, and accessories. Approximate dimensions 2.4 × 2.7 × 2.4 m. Includes transport, assembly, dismantling, cleaning, maintenance and management costs, and preparation of the support base.								
34	99.1.XB1.05.A	Price – first month								
			Total	-	1.00			1.00	€ 589.95	€ 589.95
35	99.1.XB1.05.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first								
			/ month	5.00				5.00		
			Total	/ month				5.00	€ 252.86	€ 1 264.30
	99.1.XB1.08	CONSTRUCTION SITE BOX FOR MEETING ROOM USE Supply and installation of a construction site box for use as a meeting room, consisting of a base structure elevated from the ground with folded steel profiles, roof and cladding with sandwich panels made of inner and outer sheet metal and central insulation, internal partitions in sandwich panels, aluminum fixtures, wooden floor covered with PVC. Complete with electrical system and electric heating/cooling, equipped with a desk, 6 chairs, furniture, and various accessories. Approximate dimensions 2.4 × 6.4 × 2.4 m. Includes transport, assembly, dismantling, cleaning, maintenance and management costs, and preparation of the support base.								
36	99.1.XB1.08.A	Price – first month								
			Total	-	1.00			1.00	€ 654.13	€ 654.13
37	99.1.XB1.08.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first								
			/ month	5.00				5.00		
			Total	/ month				5.00	€ 245.10	€ 1 225.50
38	99.2.OZ1.04	SCAFFOLDING GROUNDING CONNECTION Installation of a grounding connection for scaffolding as part of the lightning protection system (to be provided every 25 m along the scaffold plan with a minimum of two down-conductors at the ends), executed with 35 mm ² insulated copper conductor connected to a 2.5 m galvanized steel ground rod driven into the soil. Price per down-conductor.								
			Total	a corpo	1.00			1.00	€ 95.14	€ 95.14
	99.2.OZ1.05	GROUNDING SYSTEM FOR CONSTRUCTION SITE Installation of a grounding system for the construction site, consisting of 2.5 m galvanized steel rods interconnected with bare 35 mm ² copper conductor, including connection to the main grounding busbar using 16 mm ² insulated cable, including excavation and backfilling.								
39	99.2.OZ1.05.A	Power up to 6 kW – 2 rods								
			Total	a corpo	1.00			1.00	€ 323.20	€ 323.20
	99.2.QZ1.09	CONSTRUCTION SITE DISTRIBUTION BOARD Compensation for the use of construction site distribution boards compliant with CEI 17.13/1 (EN 60439-1) and CEI 17.13/4 (EN 60439-4) standards, with IP55 protection rating, consisting of an enclosure made of insulating, impact-resistant, and self-extinguishing material for wall installation or mounting on a self-supporting stand. Equipped with triangular-key doors to prevent access by unauthorized personnel, suitable for lockable plugs, containing internal boxes with terminal blocks, IP55 interlocked socket outlets, and boxes complete with circuit breakers with 6 kA breaking capacity and 0.03 A residual current protection. Includes connection of the supply line via external fixed plug or terminal block, emergency indicator push button installed on the external board frame complete with trip coil on the main switch, CEI 17.13/4 (EN 60439-4) certification, wiring, electrical connections, accessory works, and finishing. Includes removal at the end of use.								
40	99.2.QZ1.09.A	Board including 3 sockets 2P+T 16 A and 1 socket 3P+T 16 A Board including 3 sockets 2P+T 16 A and 1 socket 3P+T 16 A, complete with circuit breakers and 4P residual current main switch – 40 A – 0.03 A								
			Total	/ month	6.00			6.00	€ 43.40	€ 260.40

	99.2.QZ1.10	PORTABLE ELECTRICAL BOARD Compensation for the use of portable construction site electrical boards compliant with CEI 17.13/1 (EN 60439-1) and CEI 17.13/4 (EN 60439-4) standards, with IP55 protection rating, consisting of a thermoplastic, double-insulated, impact-resistant, and self-extinguishing enclosure, suitable for mounting on a stand or portable use with cable and plug. Equipped with IP55 socket outlets, circuit breakers with 6 kA breaking capacity, and 0.03 A residual current protection. Electrical connections included.								
41	99.2.QZ1.10.A	3 sockets 2P+T 16 A, complete with 2P residual current circuit breaker – 16 A – 0.03 A								
			/ month	6.00				6.00		
			Total / month					6.00	€ 6.30	€ 37.80
	99.3.AH2.04	ROCK GUARD CANOPY Construction of rock guard canopy using a tubular frame with joints or prefabricated structure and 4 cm thick wooden planks, including transport, assembly, dismantling, and removal.								
42	99.3.AH2.04.A	Projection 1.2 m								
			/ month	5.00	2.00			10.00		
			Total / month					10.00	€ 3.60	€ 36.00
	99.3.AH2.15	PREFABRICATED FRAME SCAFFOLDING FOR CONSTRUCTION Construction of authorized fixed construction scaffolding, mainly consisting of prefabricated frames, at any height, complete with suitable anchors, working platforms with toe boards, compliant external and internal guardrails (where required), special components, underscaffolds, and platforms with trapdoors and access ladders. The price includes rental, transport, periodic maintenance, dismantling, and strict compliance with current health and safety regulations on construction sites. Also included is the executive design indicating, among other things, the maximum loads per square meter of platform, the location of supports and anchors, and any necessary structural calculations according to NTC regulations. Measurement will be made per square meter of useful vertical projection of the scaffold façade. Useful area is defined as the area limited by the actual length of the scaffold and the height measured from the base plates to the top guardrail of the last platform, including fall protection devices (guardrails compliant with UNI EN 13374 or scaffolding compliant with UNI 11927) where required. Any internal cantilevers made with tubes and joints, including metal or wooden platforms properly fixed, will be evaluated separately under items C and D.								
43	99.3.AH2.15.A	Price – first month								
			West elevation – front	m2	34.04		10.80	367.63		
			East elevation – rear	m2	34.04		10.80	367.63		
			North elevation	m2	9.03		10.80	97.52		
			South elevation	m2	9.03		10.80	97.52		
			Total	m2				930.31	€ 15.84	€ 14 736.14
44	99.3.AH2.15.B	Price – for each subsequent month or fraction of a month after the first								
			see item n. 340	m2/mnt	4651.50			4 651.50		
			Total	m2/mnt				4 651.50	€ 3.83	€ 17 815.25
	99.3.AH2.17	MOBILE WORK TOWER (TRABATTELLO) Construction of a mobile work tower (compliant with UNI EN 1004 and/or D.Lgs. 81/2008), commonly called “trabattello,” consisting of prefabricated elements on at least four swivel wheels, complete with working and intermediate platforms with trapdoors, toe boards, compliant guardrails, bracing elements, stabilizing poles, and access ladders, as well as anchors where required. The price includes rental, transport, periodic maintenance, dismantling, and strict compliance with current health and safety regulations on construction sites.								
45	99.3.AH2.17.A	Mobile work tower with working platform height up to 4 m, per month or fraction thereof, including assembly								
			/ month	5.00				5.00		
			Total / month					5.00	€ 51.91	€ 259.55
			Total Safety							€ 48 562.21
			Total COMMON WORKS							€ 48 562.21
	L1		ABOVE-GROUND WORKS							€ 157 087.98
	02		Structural works							€ 126 927.01
	03		Building works							€ 30 160.96
	L2		BELOW-GROUND WORKS							€ 181 517.47
	01		Excavations and backfilling							€ 51 407.08
	02		Structural works							€ 115 223.83
	03		Building works							€ 14 886.56
	L3		COMMON WORKS							€ 48 562.21
	04		Safety							€ 48 562.21
	TOT		TOTAL WORK AMOUNT							€ 387 167.65

PA.02

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER
One-sided for single-leaf masonry

One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.
- GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a $\varnothing 12$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments < 3%.
- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;
- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm.
Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	40.00	0.45 €	18.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	1.00	46.78 €	46.78 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.58	3.50 €	2.03 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	1.10 €	1.10 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.58	27.20 €	15.78 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.55	30.28 €	16.65 €
					100.34 €
	Transport expenses	2%			2.01 €
	General expenses	15%			15.35 €
	Company profit	10%			11.77 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 129.47 €

PA.03.1 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Two-sided with steel ties

Two-sided structural reinforcement of concrete walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, metal connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBMesh66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.
- Stainless steel connectors for transverse connections, at a rate of 6/m², consisting of M8 threaded rods passing through $\varnothing 12$ holes, with 50x1.5 mm washer and nut, grade 8.8, at both wall sides.
- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;
- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with hydraulic cement mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 5 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 25 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both faces of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	CEMENT MORTAR FOR WALL CONSOLIDATION, average thickness of 5 cm.	m ²	2.00	26.03 €	52.06 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBMesh 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices(n° 6/m ²)	m ²	2.00	23.34 €	46.68 €
Materials	Stainless steel type AISI 316 - M8 bars, average length 50 cm (n° 6/m ²)	Kg.	1.183	17.79 €	21.04 €
Materials	Stainless steel type AISI 316 - M8 bolt with 50 mm diameter, 1.5 mm thick washer (n° 6/m ²)	Kg.	0.555	17.79 €	9.86 €
Materials	Chemical vinylester anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.339	23.00 €	7.80 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	3.50 €	4.06 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	2.00	1.10 €	2.20 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	27.20 €	31.55 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	30.28 €	33.31 €
					208.57 €
	Transport expenses	2%			4.17 €
	General expenses	15%			31.91 €
	Company profit	10%			24.46 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 269.11 €

PA.04

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

Surcharge for corner connection

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of connections at masonry corners, by using the corner element FBANG66X66T96 by Fibrenet, or equivalent, featuring CE marking, preformed with a 90° bend, consisting of a square mesh with 66x66 mm openings, manufactured with Alkali-Resistant glass roving and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with nominal strand diameter exceeding 3 mm and a width of 33 cm per side. Tensile strength of the composite ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of the individual bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile modulus of elasticity $\geq 25,000$ N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of the individual bar ≥ 4.14 kN, average elongation at failure 1.78%, characteristic node tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity in humid, alkaline, and saline environments $< 8\%$.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: All that is necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with best practice.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment required for the execution of the work, any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and anything else not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Corner element in GFRP FBANG66X66T96AR, 33 cm width per side	m	1.00	17.75 €	17.75 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	27.20 €	2.72 €
					20.47 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.41 €
	General expenses	15%			3.13 €
	Company profit	10%			2.40 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m 26.41 €

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

PA.05 Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors, and across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of the connections of the CRM system with the foundation and across floors, as well as across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections, by using M8 stainless steel threaded bars in Ø12 diameter holes, and thermosetting vinylester epoxy resin, applied at a rate of 3/m. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents., and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 90 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.065	17.79 €	18.94 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.203	23.00 €	4.68 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.06	3.50 €	0.21 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.06	27.20 €	1.63 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.06	30.28 €	1.82 €
					27.28 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.55 €
	General expenses	15%			4.17 €
	Company profit	10%			3.20 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m 35.20 €

PA.06 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER
Surcharge for connection across unsymmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of wall T-junctions using M8 stainless steel threaded bars embedded in a passing-through hole of diameter Ø12, M8 bolt, 50x1.5 washer, load-distribution device made of preformed mesh in glass fiber reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, calculated at 3/m. The bar is anchored to the masonry at the hole and embedded in the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 80 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.170	17.79 €	20.81 €
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 bolt + washer diameter 50 mm thickness 1.5 mm (3/ml)	Kg.	0.069	17.79 €	1.23 €
Materials	GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (3/m);	m ²	0.27	17.75 €	4.79 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.170	23.00 €	3.90 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.10	3.50 €	0.35 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	27.20 €	2.72 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.10	30.28 €	3.03 €
					36.83 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.74 €
	General expenses	15%			5.64 €
	Company profit	10%			4.32 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m 47.52 €

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX C_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – CRM strengthened status

NO STRUCTURAL MEASURES APPLIED IN BASEMENT

- vault
- old brick masonry
- CRM on wall side
- wall thickness - single/double sided CRM

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PRO-SIS

ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana
Basement, CRM strengthened

Scale **1:100**
Dim. in cm

Sheet n° **3.4-C1**

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX C_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – CRM strengthened status

- vault
- old brick masonry
- CRM on wall side
- wall thickness - single/double sided CRM

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PRO-SIS

ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana

Ground floor, CRM strengthened

Scale **1:100**
Dim. in cm

Sheet n° **3.4-C2**

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX C_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – CRM strengthened status

- vault
- old brick masonry
- CRM on wall side
- wall thickness - single/double sided CRM

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PRO-SIS

ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana	Scale 1:100 Dim. in cm	Sheet n° 3.4-C3
First floor, CRM strengthened		

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX C_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – CRM strengthened status

- vault
- old brick masonry
- CRM on wall side
- wall thickness - single/double sided CRM

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ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana

Second floor, CRM strengthened

Scale
1:100
Dim. in cm

Sheet n°
3.4-C4

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX C_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – CRM strengthened status

- vault
- old brick masonry
- CRM on wall side
- wall thickness - single/double sided CRM

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PRO-SIS

ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana

Attic, CRM strengthened

Scale
1:100
Dim. in cm

Sheet n°
3.4-C5

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX C_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – CRM strengthened status

DETAIL 75-s, 60-s, 45-s, 30-s

DETAIL 30-d, 45-d

DETAIL 15-s

DETAIL I

DETAIL A

DETAIL B

DETAIL C

DETAIL D

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX C_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – CRM strengthened status

DETAIL E

DETAIL H

DETAIL F

DETAIL L

DETAIL G

DETAIL K

DETAIL J

DETAIL M

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX C_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – CRM strengthened status

Longitudinal cross section A-A

- GFRP mesh 66 x 66
- GFRP mesh 66 x 66, horizontal layout
- GFRP connector + mesh 66 x 66
- GFRP pre-formed angle 90° in corners, length 200 cm, overlap 20 cm
- stainless steel connector bar M8 3 bars/m
 $l_{\text{anchor}} = 60 \text{ } \varnothing = 48 \text{ cm, tot.length} = 166 \text{ cm}$
- stainless steel bended anchor bar M8 3 bars/m
 $l_{\text{anchor}} = 60 \text{ } \varnothing = 48 \text{ cm in hole } \varnothing 18 \text{ mm, cement grout, tot.length} = 166 \text{ cm}$

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PRO-SIS

ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana

Cross sections, CRM strengthened

Scale **1:100**
Dim. in cm

Sheet n° **3.4-C8**

Longitudinal cross section C-C

- GFRP mesh 66 x 66
- GFRP mesh 66 x 66, horizontal layout
- GFRP connector + mesh 66 x 66
- GFRP pre-formed angle 90° in corners, length 200 cm, overlap 20 cm
- stainless steel connector bar M8 3 bars/m
 $l_{\text{anchor}} = 60 \text{ } \varnothing = 48 \text{ cm, tot.length} = 166 \text{ cm}$
- stainless steel bended anchor bar M8 3 bars/m
 $l_{\text{anchor}} = 60 \text{ } \varnothing = 48 \text{ cm in hole } \varnothing 18 \text{ mm, cement grout, tot.length} = 166 \text{ cm}$

Longitudinal cross section B-B

- GFRP mesh 66 x 66
- GFRP mesh 66 x 66, horizontal layout
- GFRP connector + mesh 66 x 66
- GFRP pre-formed angle 90° in corners, length 200 cm, overlap 20 cm
- stainless steel connector bar M8 3 bars/m
 $l_{\text{anchor}} = 60 \text{ } \varnothing = 48 \text{ cm, tot.length} = 166 \text{ cm}$
- stainless steel bended anchor bar M8 3 bars/m
 $l_{\text{anchor}} = 60 \text{ } \varnothing = 48 \text{ cm in hole } \varnothing 18 \text{ mm, cement grout, tot.length} = 166 \text{ cm}$

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PRO-SIS

ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana

Cross sections, CRM strengthened

Scale
1:100
Dim. in cm

Sheet n°
3.4-C10

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX C_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – CRM strengthened status

Transversal cross section A'-A'

Transversal cross section B'-B'

- GFRP mesh 66 x 66
- GFRP mesh 66 x 66, horizontal layout
- GFRP connector + mesh 66 x 66
- GFRP pre-formed angle 90° in corners, length 200 cm, overlap 20 cm
- stainless steel connector bar M8 3 bars/m
 $l_{\text{anchor}} = 60 \text{ } \varnothing = 48 \text{ cm, tot.length} = 166 \text{ cm}$
- stainless steel bended anchor bar M8 3 bars/m
 $l_{\text{anchor}} = 60 \text{ } \varnothing = 48 \text{ cm in hole } \varnothing 18 \text{ mm, cement grout, tot.length} = 166 \text{ cm}$

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ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana

Cross sections, CRM strengthened

Scale
1:100
Dim. in cm

Sheet n°
3.4-C11

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX C_Structural drawings of the ZVKDS building in Ljubljana – CRM strengthened status

Transversal cross section C'-C'

Transversal cross section D'-D'

distribution of:
GFRP mesh | GFRP angle

- GFRP mesh 66 x 66
- GFRP mesh 66 x 66, horizontal layout
- GFRP connector + mesh 66 x 66
- GFRP pre-formed angle 90° in corners, length 200 cm, overlap 20 cm
- stainless steel connector bar M8 3 bars/m
 $l_{\text{anchor}} = 60 \text{ } \varnothing = 48 \text{ cm, tot.length} = 166 \text{ cm}$
- stainless steel bended anchor bar M8 3 bars/m
 $l_{\text{anchor}} = 60 \text{ } \varnothing = 48 \text{ cm in hole } \varnothing 18 \text{ mm, cement grout, tot.length} = 166 \text{ cm}$

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PRO-SIS

ZVKDS building, Slovenska 28, Ljubljana
Cross sections, CRM strengthened

Scale
1:100
Dim. in cm

Sheet n°
3.4-C12

PRO-SIS Report 3.4 - ANNEX D - Bill of quantities for the strengthening of the building of ZVKDS in Ljubljana by using the CONSTRAIN-PROSIS technology

From Slovenian price analysis

DESCRIPTION OF WORKS AND SUPPLIES	UNIT	SIMILAR	LENGTH	WIDTH	HEIGHT	QUANTITY	PRICE	AMOUNT
WORKS ABOVE GROUND								
Structural works								
<p>PA02 - STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - One-sided for single-leaf masonry</p> <p>One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%. - GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a $\varnothing 12$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments <3%. - Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection; - Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent. <p>The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.</p> <p>EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements.</p> <p>Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.</p> <p>Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.</p>								
<i>North Elevation</i>	<i>m2</i>					<i>463.30</i>	<i>463.30</i>	
<i>South Elevation</i>	<i>m2</i>					<i>394.10</i>	<i>394.10</i>	
<i>West Elevation</i>	<i>m2</i>					<i>226.83</i>	<i>226.83</i>	
<i>East Elevation</i>	<i>m2</i>					<i>230.98</i>	<i>230.98</i>	
<i>Stairwell</i>	<i>m2</i>					<i>152.75</i>	<i>152.75</i>	
<i>Internal walls</i>	<i>m2</i>					<i>351.17</i>	<i>351.17</i>	
<i>Total</i>	<i>m2</i>					<i>351.17</i>	<i>1 819.13</i>	€ 119.58 € 217 531.57

PA.02 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER					
One-sided for single-leaf masonry					
<p>One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>Preformed mesh</u> made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%. - GFRP "L" shape composite material <u>connectors</u> FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a $\varnothing 12$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments < 3%. - <u>Load distribution devices</u> made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection; - <u>Chemical anchor</u> for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent. <p>The system is completed with premixed lime-based <u>plaster mortar</u> for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.</p> <p>EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.</p> <p>Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.</p>					
CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	40.00	0.45 €	18.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	1.00	46.78 €	46.78 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.58	2.47 €	1.43 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	0.82 €	0.82 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.58	22.51 €	13.06 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.55	24.36 €	13.40 €
Transport	Transport expenses				2.18 €
					95.66 €
	General expenses	15%			14.35 €
	Company profit	10%			9.57 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 119.58 €

PA.03 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Two-sided

Two-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBMESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.

- GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for transversal passing-through connection on a $\varnothing 24$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments < 3%.

- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;

- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both faces of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	80.00	0.45 €	36.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBMESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices(n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	2.00	46.78 €	93.56 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	2.47 €	2.87 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	2.00	0.82 €	1.63 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	22.51 €	26.11 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	24.36 €	26.80 €
Transport	Transport expenses				1.91 €
					188.87 €
	General expenses	15%			28.33 €
	Company profit	10%			18.89 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m² 236.09 €

PA.04

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

Surcharge for corner connection

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of connections at masonry corners, by using the corner element FBANG66X66T96 by FibreNet, or equivalent, featuring CE marking, preformed with a 90° bend, consisting of a square mesh with 66x66 mm openings, manufactured with Alkali-Resistant glass roving and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with nominal strand diameter exceeding 3 mm and a width of 33 cm per side. Tensile strength of the composite ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of the individual bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile modulus of elasticity $\geq 25,000$ N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of the individual bar ≥ 4.14 kN, average elongation at failure 1.78%, characteristic node tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity in humid, alkaline, and saline environments $< 8\%$.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: All that is necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with best practice.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment required for the execution of the work, any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and anything else not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Corner element in GFRP FBANG66X66T96AR, 33 cm width per side	m	1.00	17.75 €	17.75 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	22.51 €	2.25 €
					20.00 €
	General expenses	15%			3.00 €
	Company profit	10%			2.00 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m 25.00 €

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

PA.05 Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors, and across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of the connections of the CRM system with the foundation and across floors, as well as across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections, by using M8 stainless steel threaded bars in Ø12 diameter holes, and thermosetting vinylester epoxy resin, applied at a rate of 3/m. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents., and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 90 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.065	13.34 €	14.21 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.203	23.00 €	4.68 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.06	2.47 €	0.15 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.06	22.51 €	1.35 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.06	24.37 €	1.46 €
					21.85 €
	General expenses	15%			3.28 €
	Company profit	10%			2.18 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m 27.31 €

PA.06 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER
Surcharge for connection across unsymmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of wall T-junctions using M8 stainless steel threaded bars embedded in a passing-through hole of diameter Ø12, M8 bolt, 50x1.5 washer, load-distribution device made of preformed mesh in glass fiber reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, calculated at 3/m. The bar is anchored to the masonry at the hole and embedded in the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 80 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.170	13.34 €	15.61 €
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 bolt + washer diameter 50 mm thickness 1.5 mm (3/ml)	Kg.	0.069	13.34 €	0.93 €
Materials	GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (3/m);	m ²	0.27	17.75 €	4.79 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.170	23.00 €	3.90 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.10	2.47 €	0.25 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	22.51 €	2.25 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.10	24.37 €	2.44 €
					30.16 €
	General expenses	15%			4.52 €
	Company profit	10%			3.02 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m	37.70 €